

Horizon 2020 Program

Security and resilience for collaborative manufacturing environments

ICT-2019-2

A COmprehensive cyber-intelligence framework for resilient
coLLABorative manufacturing Systems

D1.1: COLLABS Innovations for Industrial IoT Systems¹

Abstract: In this deliverable we briefly summarize significant new research results and new commercial products that have been published or released on the market, since the submission of the project proposal in 28/03/2019, in the technological areas where *COLLABS* aims to advance the state-of-the-art (SotA thereafter). The goal of this document is to ensure that the starting point for these targeted advances is up to date. It thus contains one section for each technological area listed as a target for advancement in Section 1.4.1. of the proposal which describes the project's offerings beyond the SotA.

¹ *The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 871518.*

Contractual Date of Delivery	30/04/2020
Actual Date of Delivery	30/04/2020
Deliverable Security Class	Public
Editor	<i>Miloš Radovanović, UNSPMF</i>
Contributors	<i>Wafa Ben Jaballah, TSG</i>
	<i>George Bravos, ITML</i>
	<i>Andreas Brokalakis, FORTH</i>
	<i>Erwan Le-Disez, REN</i>
	<i>Ernesto Gomez Marin, IFAG</i>
	<i>Erwin Moed, PCL</i>
	<i>Md Masoom Rabbani, UNIPD</i>
	<i>Miloš Radovanović, UNSPMF</i>
	<i>Valerio Senni, Fabio Federici, ALES</i>
	<i>George Spanoudakis, Konstantinos Fysarakis, STS</i>
Quality Assurance	<i>Prabhakaran Kasinathan, Martin Wimmer, SAG Panagiotis Rizomiliotis, HUA</i>

The *COLLABS* Consortium

1	COMMISSARIAT A L ENERGIE ATOMIQUE ET AUX ENERGIES ALTERNATIVES	CEA	France	1	36
2	IDRYMA TECHNOLOGIAS KAI EREVNAS	FORTH	Greece	1	36
3	PHILIPS CONSUMER LIFESTYLE BV	PCL	Netherlands	1	36
4	INFINEON TECHNOLOGIES AG	IFAG	Germany	1	36
5	ADVANCED LABORATORY ON EMBEDDED SYSTEMS SRL	ALES	Italy	1	36
6	UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD FACULTY OF SCIENCES	UNSPMF	Serbia	1	36
7	SPHYNX TECHNOLOGY SOLUTIONS AG	STS	Switzerland	1	36
8	THALES SIX GTS FRANCE SAS	TSG	France	1	36
9	INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY FOR MARKET LEADERSHIP	ITML	Greece	1	36
10	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI PADOVA	UNIPD	Italy	1	36
11	SIEMENS AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT	SAG	Germany	1	36
12	RENAULT SAS	REN	France	1	36
13	HAROKOPIO UNIVERSITY	HUA	Greece	1	36

Document Revisions & Quality Assurance

Internal Reviewers

1. *Prabhakaran Kasinathan, Martin Wimmer, SAG*
2. *Panagiotis Rizomiliotis, HUA*

Revisions

Version	Date	By	Overview
COLLABS.D1.1.4	29/04/2020	Editor	Final document.
COLLABS.D1.1.3	21/04/2020	#1, #2	Comments on first draft.
COLLABS.D1.1.2	08/04/2020	Editor	First draft.
COLLABS.D1.1.1	04/03/2020	#1, #2	Comments on the ToC.
COLLABS.D1.1.0	21/02/2020	Editor	ToC.

Table of Contents

LIST OF FIGURES	5
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	6
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	7
1 INTRODUCTION	8
1.1 SMART MANUFACTURING ECOSYSTEM	9
1.2 MAIN FUNCTIONAL COMPONENTS	10
1.3 MULTI-LEVEL SECURITY MECHANISM	11
2 DATA PROTECTION	13
2.1 PROPOSAL'S STATED OFFERING BEYOND MARCH 2019 SOTA	13
2.2 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH ADVANCES SINCE MARCH 2019	14
2.3 OVERVIEW OF INNOVATIVE COMMERCIAL PRODUCTS RELEASED SINCE MARCH 2019	14
3 DISTRIBUTED ANOMALY DETECTION AND REMOTE ATTESTATION IN INDUSTRIAL IOT SYSTEMS	17
3.1 PROPOSAL'S STATED OFFERING BEYOND MARCH 2019 SOTA	17
3.2 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH ADVANCES SINCE MARCH 2019	18
3.3 OVERVIEW OF INNOVATIVE COMMERCIAL PRODUCTS RELEASED SINCE MARCH 2019	21
4 PHYSICAL SECURITY	23
4.1 PROPOSAL'S STATED OFFERING BEYOND MARCH 2019 SOTA	23
4.2 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH ADVANCES SINCE MARCH 2019	23
4.3 OVERVIEW OF INNOVATIVE COMMERCIAL PRODUCTS RELEASED SINCE MARCH 2019	25
5 FUNCTION AS A SERVICE (FAAS)	29
5.1 PROPOSAL'S STATED OFFERING BEYOND MARCH 2019 SOTA	29
5.2 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH ADVANCES SINCE MARCH 2019	30
5.3 OVERVIEW OF INNOVATIVE COMMERCIAL PRODUCTS RELEASED SINCE MARCH 2019	30
6 SECURE AND TRUSTED EXECUTION ENVIRONMENTS	34
6.1 PROPOSAL'S STATED OFFERING BEYOND MARCH 2019 SOTA	34
6.2 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH ADVANCES SINCE MARCH 2019	35
6.3 OVERVIEW OF INNOVATIVE COMMERCIAL PRODUCTS RELEASED SINCE MARCH 2019	36
7 ENCRYPTED TRAFFIC ANALYSIS	38
7.1 PROPOSAL'S STATED OFFERING BEYOND MARCH 2019 SOTA	38
7.2 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH ADVANCES SINCE MARCH 2019	38
7.3 OVERVIEW OF INNOVATIVE COMMERCIAL PRODUCTS RELEASED SINCE MARCH 2019	40
8 AI-ENABLED CYBERSECURITY IN IIOT-BASED COLLABORATIVE MANUFACTURING ENVIRONMENTS	41
8.1 PROPOSAL'S STATED OFFERING BEYOND MARCH 2019 SOTA	41
8.2 OVERVIEW OF RESEARCH ADVANCES SINCE MARCH 2019	41
8.3 OVERVIEW OF INNOVATIVE COMMERCIAL PRODUCTS RELEASED SINCE MARCH 2019	43
9 CONCLUSION	44
REFERENCES	45

List of Figures

Figure 1: <i>COLLABS</i> cyber-intelligence digital collaboration framework.	9
Figure 2: ExtraHop Reveal(x).	15
Figure 3: Nozomi Networks solution.	16
Figure 4: FaaS in comparison with other cloud computing paradigms.	29
Figure 5: The Enveil security solution.	31
Figure 6: Secret Computing concept.	31
Figure 7: Cybernetica Sharemind secure analytics.	32
Figure 8: Duality SecurePlus Platform.	32

List of Abbreviations

ABAC	Attribute-Based Access Control
ABE	Attribute-Based Encryption
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CC	Common Criteria
COLLABS	A COmprehensive cyber-intelligence framework for resilient coLLABorative manufacturing Systems
DTCB	Distributed Trusted Computing Base
DL	Deep Learning
DLT	Distributed Ledger Technology
FaaS	Function as a Service
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HE	Homomorphic Encryption
HW	HardWare
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
ML	Machine Learning
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
OT	Operational Technology
PKI	Public Key Infrastructure
RA	Remote Attestation
RTM	Root of Trust for Measurement
S&P	Security and Privacy
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software Defined Networking
SGX	Software Guard eXtensions
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMC	Secure Multiparty Computation
SOC	Security Operations Centre
SotA	State-of-the-Art
SW	SoftWare
TCB	Trusted Computing Base
TEE	Trusted Execution Environment
TLS	Transport Layer Security

Executive Summary

In this deliverable we briefly summarize significant new research results and new commercial products that have been published or released on the market, since the submission of the project proposal in 28/03/2019, in the technological areas where *COLLABS* aims to advance the state-of-the-art (SotA thereafter). The goal of this document is to ensure that the starting point for these targeted advances is up to date. It thus contains one section for each technological area listed as a target for advance in Section 1.4.1. of the proposal which describes the project's offerings beyond the SotA.

The deliverable is organized as follows. The introductory Section 1 briefly describes the overall setting and the main problem addressed by *COLLABS*, its project statement and the structure of the proposed *COLLABS* framework, in order to provide context for the sections that follow. Sections 2–8 respectively focus on the SotA in areas of: data protection (Section 2), distributed anomaly detection and remote attestation (Section 3), physical security (Section 4), function as a service (FaaS, Section 5), secure and trusted execution environments (Section 6), encrypted traffic analysis (Section 7), and AI-enabled cybersecurity in IIoT-based collaborative manufacturing environments (Section 8). Section 9 concludes the deliverable with a summary of the impacts of the new SotA on project implementation and the outlook of its contribution.

During the past year there have been many works in the domains relevant to *COLLABS*, notably in blockchain applications, machine- and deep-learning based anomaly detection and wireless system design, remote attestation for tackling security issues in IoT systems, implementations of secure multiparty computation (SMC) and homomorphic encryption (HE), platforms providing trusted execution environments (TEEs), encrypted network traffic analysis for various purposes, and (distributed) machine learning in different levels of cybersecurity for IIoT systems. These works, overviewed in this document, provide a strong foundation for *COLLABS* project implementation without jeopardizing its goals with relation to SotA advancements.

1 Introduction

The recent proliferation of advances in information and communication technologies (ICTs), as well as convergence of operational technology (OT) and information technology (IT), are currently the main underlying factors behind the increasing pace of expansion of *industrial automation*. This rapid expansion can be viewed as an ongoing “phase transition” in manufacturing, and is often termed *the fourth industrial revolution* or “*Industry 4.0*”. Key contributors to this revolution are the fields of the industrial Internet of things (IIoT), Big Data analytics, and artificial intelligence (AI). Their interplay in the context of huge numbers of devices embedded into industrial systems coupled with information exchange and analysis enables the creation of industrial systems that are intelligent, autonomous and remotely operated. The revolution is bound to challenge traditional digital boundaries among industrial systems, since the flow of information in the manufacturing chain will need to cross the boundaries so that full-scale digital collaboration between production entities becomes a reality.

The envisioned advances, however, come with their own set of problems, the key one being the exponential growth of security risks stemming from the increased connectedness of manufacturing systems. Security incidents involving the manufacturing industry have increased in number recently, placing it among the top ten most targeted industries in 2019². Unfortunately, Industry 4.0 is prone to complex and sophisticated attacks at each control point of the manufacturing process, making it imperative to invest special effort into defences against cyber-attacks, everywhere from the network level up to the host level.

In order to meet the challenges outlined above, the *COLLABS Project Statement* promises the following: “*COLLABS* will develop, validate, demonstrate, and support a comprehensive *cyber-intelligence framework for collaborative manufacturing*, which enables the secure data exchange across the digital supply chain while providing high degree of resilience, reliability, accountability and trustworthiness, and addresses threat prevention, detection, mitigation, and real-time response. *COLLABS* will achieve these goals by utilising state-of-the-art technologies and making significant scientific and technological advances in several key domains, including *secure multi-party computations and homomorphic encryption, distributed deep learning and anomaly detection, distributed ledger technologies (blockchain) and smart contracts, and distributed remote software attestation*. *COLLABS* will significantly contribute to realising industrial and societal opportunities of collaborative manufacturing, by validating and demonstrating its framework on *3 real-world use cases coming from complementary Industry 4.0 manufacturing domains* and delivering an *Industry 4.0 Experimentation Lab*.”

The *COLLABS* cyber-intelligence digital collaboration framework is illustrated in Figure 1. The framework is by nature and necessity a complex system involving multiple infrastructure elements, multiple stakeholders, etc. Sections 2–8 of this deliverable will focus on specific technological aspects of the framework where the project is expected to produce offerings beyond the state-of-the-art. In order to provide overall context, the remainder of this section will briefly describe the framework through three viewpoints/dimensions:

- i. The smart manufacturing ecosystem (Section 1.1) of physically entangled systems involving the digital supply network (Section 1.1.1), smart factory (Section 1.1.2), and connected objects (Section 1.1.3);

² IBM X-Force Threat Intelligence Index 2020: <https://www.ibm.com/security/data-breach/threat-intelligence>

- ii. Main functional components of the framework (Section 1.2), namely those for data exchange (Section 1.2.1); data protection (Section 1.2.2); threat protection, monitoring, and prevention (Section 1.2.3); and threat detection, mitigation and real-time response (Section 1.2.4);
- iii. Multi-level security mechanism of the framework (Section 1.3), including hardware-enabled and device-level security (Section 1.3.1); inter-device security based on ledger technologies (Section 1.3.2), and machine learning-based inter-device cognitive security (Section 1.3.3).

Figure 1: COLLABS cyber-intelligence digital collaboration framework.

1.1 Smart manufacturing ecosystem

The main elements of the smart manufacturing environment (see Figure 1) include the digital supply network, smart factory, and connected objects, described in Sections 1.1.1, 1.1.2 and 1.1.3, respectively.

1.1.1 The digital supply networks

This is the “broadest” scale of the system, corresponding to external entities within the supply chain with which a smart factory needs to exchange information. A key driving factor for the successful and rapid growth of a digital collaboration ecosystem within a digital supply network is *trusted data exchange*.

In order to realise effective and trusted data exchange, *COLLABS* will employ *strong cryptography schemes* for data communication that conform to IoT constraints (performance, volumes, management), and a public key infrastructure (PKI) scheme for source authentication, to protect against communication manipulation. *COLLABS* will also provide a highly secure data environment, allowing the data owner to execute full control over authentication levels for data access. To this end the framework will utilise *workflows enforced by a distributed consensus protocol* across the digital supply network.

Secure multiparty computations, homomorphic encryption, differential privacy methods, and trusted execution environments will be employed for the highest level of data protection in order to protect sensitive data from unauthorised access. Trusted built-in ***functions as a service*** (FaaS – for example, machine learning tasks, statistical functions, etc.) will also be offered to ease deployment. In addition, ***blockchain technologies*** will be leveraged to ensure the integrity of network transactions, thus enabling the ***decentralised exchange of trusted data***. This is important for IIoT and its applications, since data integrity and security can be ensured while maintaining device interoperability.

1.1.2 The smart factory

This is a “middle” scale element of the system, which includes the factory internal devices and their interconnections within its communication, storage, and processing infrastructure.

The ***COLLABS*** framework will offer defences against different types of attacks that may arise within the smart factory, through an approach that combines IT and OT by considering both the digital processes and the machinery and objects that could be impacted. This will be achieved by installing ***hardware-based security modules*** and creating a ***secure IoT network environment***, thereby ensuring data integrity while protecting networks in the IoT communication environment. The solution will employ PKI technologies to provide certificates for devices and users that will be used for authentication.

The secure environment for IoT devices will be created using technologies such as the Intel Software Guard eXtensions (SGX). This technology protects selected code and data from disclosure or modification at the processor level, and is available in the majority of recent Intel processors. Data protection and privacy in data transfers is assured through SGX’s ***remote attestation*** technology. Using the SGX remote attestation flow, a client will be able to “attest” to a remote entity that it is “trusted,” thereby establishing an authenticated communication channel. Federated and heterogeneous cloud environments will be given special attention for adoption of the Intel SGX technology.

1.1.3 Connected objects

This term refers to the “lowest” scale of the system consisting of individual devices (like IIoT sensors) interconnected within the manufacturing environment, which are often vulnerable, e.g., because of limited upgrade and patching capabilities. Adversaries can compromise IoT nodes, especially wireless and mobile ones, through reverse engineering and physical replacement, or forgery of the devices’ cryptographic credentials. An emerging approach addressing attacks at this level involves identifying and extracting ***unique device fingerprints*** that can be established by collecting and analysing received (radio) signals and protocol data.

1.2 Main functional components

The functional organisation of ***COLLABS*** consists of four main elements: Unified data exchange platform (Section 1.2.1), Data protection mechanisms (Section 1.2.2), Threat protection, prevention and monitoring (Section 1.2.3) and Threat detection and response (Section 1.2.4).

1.2.1 Unified data exchange platform

The data exchange platform will be responsible for connecting the manufacturing facilities with external partners in the value chain. The ***COLLABS*** framework will implement a secure and robust data exchange platform which incorporates ***secure multi-party computation*** (SMC), ***homomorphic encryption*** (HE), ***distributed ledgers***, and ***differential privacy***.

1.2.2 Data protection mechanisms

This element provides solutions to efficiently protect the data by means of access control and data loss prevention.

Comprehensive Access Control: Distributed PKI will be used for user and device authentication, removing the reliance on passwords where feasible. To eliminate the possibility of forgery, the certificates will be managed in a blockchain. The *attribute-based access control* (ABAC) paradigm will allow fine-grained and flexible definition of data access rules.

Data Loss Prevention (DLP): Solutions for discovering all types of confidential data will be offered, which employ content-aware detection methodologies and predefined contextual signatures. The solutions will be based on regular expression matching aided by deep learning techniques to automate classification, monitoring and detection of sensitive data.

1.2.3 Threat protection, prevention and monitoring

Threat protection will be achieved through the use of “low-level” remote attestation technology and “high-level” advanced protection involving machine learning approaches.

Remote attestation in distributed Industrial IoT systems: Compromising unprotected IoT devices can be done relatively easily by, for example, modifying a device’s firmware, as a precursor to a large-scale attack. Remote attestation can be used as an efficient means of preventing such attacks by verification of software integrity. However, current remote attestation mechanisms do not consider inter-device interaction flow. Further difficulties also remain, such as lack of scalability to large numbers of devices, compromised dynamicity, and performance issues regarding communication and computation overhead.

Advanced Threat Protection (ATP): In addition to monitoring threats against previously identified signatures, the *COLLABS* framework will employ *deep learning* (DL) and *machine learning* (ML) techniques, enabling the system to monitor a wider range of evolving threat vectors. Such approaches can be fostered to effectively track malicious behaviour and improve predictive analysis of threats and attacks.

1.2.4 Threat detection and response

This component addresses threat detection and implementation of countermeasures, as well as evolution and real-time response when needed. Within the *COLLABS* framework, it will be based on new systems that will use *model checking and attribution* mechanisms to identify abnormal or malicious events. Decentralised collaborative threat intelligence will be offered, through the use of *distributed ledger mechanisms*.

1.3 Multi-level security mechanism

As can be seen in Figure 1, *COLLABS* security will be implemented on three levels, from lowest to highest, respectively: Level 1 – hardware-enabled and device-level security (Section 1.3.1), Level 2 – Inter-device level security based on distributed ledger technologies (Section 1.3.2), and Level 3 – Machine learning-based cognitive security level (Section 1.3.3).

1.3.1 Level 1: Hardware-enabled and device-level security

Security at the lowest level of the architecture will include multiple hardware-enabled mechanisms, such as *device fingerprinting and hardening*, *SGX-based generation of data enclaves*, and the use of *hardware security components*, developed by project partners. Unique device fingerprints will be captured both by collecting and analysing received radio signals and protocol data via an AI-based profiler that will use features extracted from received physical signal (RSS or CSI) and radio-interface protocol data (time stamps or interarrival times) for

device identification. Resilience of the system in the event of physical access or theft will be enhanced by storing keys in protected memory regions of dedicated chips.

1.3.2 Level 2: Inter-device level security based on distributed ledger technologies

In the security setting at the second level of the architecture, proper functioning, resilience and safety of the network and device-to-device communication will be ensured by implementing *service-level agreements* (SLAs) or *smart contracts*. The *COLLABS* framework will also involve *distributed ledgers (blockchain)*, *software defined networking* (SDN), and *network function virtualisation* (NFV).

1.3.3 Level 3: Machine learning-based cognitive security level

The framework will monitor data flows between devices in order to create situational awareness and implement *cognitive security mechanisms*, including *model-based checking*, *software analysis and monitoring*, *ML-based anomaly detection*, etc. Most importantly, at this level security will be implemented primarily on *encrypted network flows*.

2 Data protection

2.1 Proposal's stated offering beyond March 2019 SotA

With Industry 4.0 and IIoT, the focus is primarily on data and the exchange of data across all system boundaries (Leuze electronic, 2019), which nevertheless increases the related risks (Hirschmann, 2015). The Smart Factory (Section 1.1.2) will need to adopt security functions in a holistic and structured manner, including the use of: (i) Encryption; (ii) Access Control; (iii) Creation of zones and conduits; and (iv) Authentication.

Moreover, the huge number of stakeholders involved (customers, suppliers, manufacturers, logistic providers, etc) and the numerous parties providing data critical to the overall value chain comprise a diverse setup that does not work well with a centralised trust authority. Distributed consensus protocols offer an interesting solution. In this context, blockchain, which is designed for resilience and relies on well-established cryptographic tools and distributed consensus mechanisms, can provide key benefits, such as persistence, fault-tolerance, auditability, and data integrity. Public blockchains (e.g. Bitcoin, Ethereum) show limitations when applied to industrial use cases (Fernández-Caramés and Fraga-Lamas, May 2018). Indeed, aspects such as controlled data reversibility, data privacy, transactions volume scalability, system responsiveness and ease of protocol updatability³, which are crucial for most corporate applications, are not fully covered by the first generation of blockchain technologies. These shortcomings led to the development of alternative blockchain technologies, which can generally be classified into two categories: private (one participant extends the immutable ledger) and consortium (members share the authority among them) blockchains; examples include Quorum⁴, Multichain⁵, and Hyperledger Fabric⁶. Applications of blockchains (and distributed ledger technologies – DLTs – in general) can be distinguished into three types: use as an immutable chronological record of events, use as a currency to also transfer financial value, and smart contract use cases that formalise contractual relationships between entities. Collaborative manufacturing suggests promising applications of all three types: be it a compliance audit trail that secures the integrity of certification documents, machine time flexibility trading that allows manufacturing partners to sell or buy excess machine capacity, or a smart contract-based workflow that governs contractual obligations between collaborating manufacturers relying upon sensor data and program logic.

COLLABS innovation beyond the state-of-the-art: *COLLABS* will specify and provide fine-grained authorisation enforcement for IIoT. Relying on existing IT security standards, it will enable flexibility and dynamicity of attribute-based access control (ABAC), governed by a central policy, for devices with restricted computing and network capabilities. For “greenfield” systems and direct exchanges between devices, modern encryption techniques (such as attribute-based encryption – ABE) will enable authorisation and data confidentiality, at the nearest of the data production point. For “brownfield” systems and devices with limited network connectivity, usage of self-contained access tokens will enable data integrity, and offline authentication and authorisation enforcement at IoT gateway level. Moreover, in order to carry out data exchange across existing system boundaries, the solutions will enable the multi-tenancy of authorisation systems to share data without compromises on data protection mechanisms. For interactions

³ <https://www.initc3.org/projects.html>

⁴ <https://www.goquorum.com/>

⁵ <https://www.multichain.com/>

⁶ <https://www.hyperledger.org/projects/fabric>

between the different stakeholders without depending on a single authority, *COLLABS* will go beyond existing identity federation and access control concepts by delivering a workflow-driven security solution based on blockchain architecture, also covering mutual contractual obligations, compliance supervision, and balancing confidentiality with transparency requirements, enabling partners in collaborative manufacturing to share data in a secure and trustful manner.

2.2 Overview of research advances since March 2019

IoT security, and IIoT in specific, is a field at the limelight of the security research community, with continuous developments on new concepts and improvements on existing ones to cater for the intricacies of the domain (Yu and Guo, Aug 2019).

The IIoT-focused developments cover a range of data protection aspects, such as novel cryptography schemes for securing symmetric algorithm implementations in white-box embedded IIoT devices (Shi et al., Jul 2019), lightweight certificateless public key (Elhabob et al., Jun 2019) and digital signature (Rezaeibagha et al., Sept 2019) schemes, as well as the provision of reliable storage, convenient usage, efficient search, and secure deletion on intelligent edge IIoT devices (Yu et al., Oct 2019).

DLTs, and blockchain in specific, continue to attract significant research interest, with a significant number of recent works focusing on the intricacies of IIoT and the secure and privacy-aware management of supply chains (Gonczol et al., Jan 2020; Adams et al., Jan 2020; Mehmet et al., Dec 2019; Sani et al., Oct 2019). Several current research efforts also focus on the potential of the integration of blockchain and artificial intelligence (Ekramifard et al., Mar 2020). Moreover, the use of DLTs on supply chains is also studied in the literature as an enabler of financial inclusion and sustainability (Leong et al., Nov 2019).

Considering the project's goal to leverage blockchain to enhance security services (e.g., authentication and authorisation), as sketched in the previous subsection, a literature review reveals a number of relevant recent research advances and open challenges (Rouhani and Deters, Oct 2019) that will be considered when developing the associated *COLLABS* building blocks. Said advances cover, among others, the use of blockchain along with digital identities for service accountability (Furfaro et al., Apr 2019), decentralised authorisation and authentication schemes based on consortium blockchain (Zhang and Bai, Dec 2019). The work presented in (Alshehri and Panda, Jan 2020) is of particular interest, as it combines blockchain with ABE to build a secure and fine-grained data access control scheme that prevents smart IoT edge nodes (fog nodes) from violating data security even in cases when a compromised node is detected, while also enabling nodes to perform the authorization process in a distributed manner.

2.3 Overview of innovative commercial products released since March 2019

During the last year, a number of deployments in the market of data protection in industrial IoT environments have shown that there is significant activity in that field.

*ExtraHop Reveal(x)*⁷ was revealed in the market in June 2019; it provides advanced discovery, classification and behaviour profiling for enterprise IoT devices, providing visibility from the device to the service layer, the company said. The latest enhancements extend Reveal(x) capabilities to the enterprise IoT device edge, providing complete visibility, detection and response across the attack surface without the need for point products.

⁷ <https://www.extrahop.com/products/the-extrahop-difference/>

With the latest release, ExtraHop Reveal(x) can discover, identify and profile all IoT devices and services to deliver complete visibility without friction to IT and Security Operations teams. From there, device behaviour profiling extracts rich data from network and cloud traffic, which ExtraHop said enables deeper analysis across devices at the service level.

Meanwhile, guided investigation automatically gathers contextual information, related decisions and packet level details into a single workflow, enabling security analysts and threat hunters to quickly determine the impact and scope of an IoT event. And IoT security hygiene address issues like IoT devices and services using unencrypted communications and is capable of isolating devices in the network.

Figure 2: ExtraHop Reveal(x). [Source: <https://www.extrahop.com/products/the-extrahop-difference/>]

Nozomi Networks Version 20.0⁸ that was released towards the end of 2019 includes new groundbreaking anomaly detection technology that delivers unmatched accuracy for enterprise IoT networks. Customers / end users also now have the option of centralizing the monitoring of distributed sites via a single console that can be deployed on the Microsoft Azure cloud platform, according to the company.

A new asset intelligence service in Nozomi Networks Version 20.0 continuously updates the adaptive learning technology with OT and IoT device information to significantly improve the accuracy of alerts in constantly changing IoT environments. The latest release also allows for the deployment of the cloud management console in Microsoft Azure, allowing for centralized management of decentralized assets.

Nozomi Networks 20.0 delivers fast-performing appliances designed to meet the large-scale and high-speed requirements of today converged OT, IoT and IT networks, the company said. The latest release also includes new and improved reports designed to give enterprise customers a better understanding of their converged IT/OT network and the risks they face, according to the company.

⁸ <https://www.nozominetworks.com/products/solution-overview/>

Figure 3: Nozomi Networks solution. [Source: <https://www.nozominetworks.com/products/solution-overview/>]

Finally, *Essence SigmaDots*⁹ that reached the market in 2019 has developed a comprehensive cybersecurity tool that harnesses the power of distributed architecture to completely secure IoT devices, applications and data. The technology maximizes IoT security and minimizes the impact on the consumer by protecting the entire path, including device, network and system.

The SigmaDots platform is comprised of four pillars: on-the-edge dynamic firewall and antivirus; distributed MQTT networking protocol as a service; end-to-end encryption as a service; and cloud-agnostic/on-premises platform for cyber events, operational monitoring, and alerting. Essence said these pillars can be implemented independently or as a complete offering.

Taken together, the company said Essence SigmaDots enables complete network visibility, delivering insights into attacks and suspicious activities to the SOC, which in turn allows for a faster response.

⁹ <https://sigmadots.com>

3 Distributed anomaly detection and remote attestation in industrial IoT systems

3.1 Proposal's stated offering beyond March 2019 SotA

In a matter of two decades, the explosion of digital technologies completely changed the way we live. The digital revolution dramatically transformed communication, healthcare, financing, transport, even manufacturing and government. Although these advancements have great economic and social benefits, they also bring myriad challenges associated to security and privacy (S&P). Individuals and organizations produce, process, store, and transmit enormous amounts of (more or less) sensitive data on their own infrastructure or across a network. And as the number of connected devices they use increases and the amount of data they produce grows, so do the opportunities for their abuse. Due to this expanding attack surface, the number and complexity of threats and cyber-attacks is growing rapidly. Securing the information and communications technology (ICT) infrastructure, connected devices, and data has never been more challenging. To address these challenges, best practices and technologies need to evolve. In particular the adoption of Industry 4.0 and the IIoT make the manufacturing sector prone to cyber-attacks such as 2014 German steel mill attack (BBC News, 2014), the 2015 BlackEnergy attack in Ukraine (ICS-CERT, 2016), the 2016 Shamoon2 attack (Falcone, 2016), and the 2017 WannaCry attack (Fruhlinger, 2018), to name a few on critical infrastructures.

Distributed anomaly detection

Anomaly detection is a key task in identifying threats to industrial IoT systems in such a way as to introduce minimal communication overhead and energy consumption in the network. *COLLABS* aims to tackle this problem by employing a distributed approach. Analysis of data from the nodes can reveal misbehaviours in the network, while misbehaviours can have two causes: genuine faults and malicious activity in nodes that are compromised. Both types of misbehaviours can be identified by analysis of sensor or traffic data. *COLLABS* will propose a distributed anomaly detection method for identification of malicious behaviours. Traditional techniques such as average k-nearest neighbour distance will be employed first in order to identify anomalous clusters at the device or gateway level¹⁰.

Remote attestation as a security mechanism to safeguard IIoT systems

The large-scale population of devices that is foreseen to be connected to the internet, offers an unprecedented attack surface for hackers. This is exacerbated from the fact that connected devices typically reside in unprotected environments, are usually simple in both hardware (HW) and software (SW), and thus easily hackable. Hackers can replace the (legitimate) SW running on devices with a malware that would, for example, take part in more complex attacks, aiming to extract data or create a DoS. The impact of cyber-attacks based on connected devices can be tremendous, and the risk of being hit by such an attack is growing enormously. Just from 2016 to 2017, the number of DDoS attack attempts per month increased by 91% (DeNisco Rayome, 2017). Attacks are often caused by leveraging vulnerabilities of the SW (e.g. unconstrained memory allocation) or system configurations (e.g. weak cryptography or passwords). An effective way to assess the integrity of the firmware running on a device is remote attestation (RA). RA is an interactive protocol between a verifier and a prover, which allows the former to obtain a cryptographically secure evidence of the state of the SW running on

¹⁰ Traditional techniques for outlier detection saw rare use in (industrial) IoT literature, but recently several works appeared that suggest good potential for successful application of these techniques, as overviewed in Section 3.2.

the device (i.e., a measurement). RA usually requires HW support and relies on a root of trust for measurement (RTM), a combination of HW technologies (like TPM v2.0, Intel SGX, or ARM TrustZone) and SW; the RTM performs a measurement of the platform and computes a cryptographically secure proof of the authenticity of the measurement, delivered to the verifier. While being a well-established area in settings with one *prover* and one *verifier*, given the large scale of typical networks of connected devices, designing scalable mechanisms to support remote attestation for such deployments is of outmost importance to reduce costs and resources at the *verifier* side, as well as to ensure a timely detection of ongoing (potentially disruptive) attacks. **COLLABS** will explore existing integrity verification solutions tailored for low-end resource constrained devices especially for sensitive applications, as well as scalable ways to perform it. **COLLABS'** goal is to provide secure, resource efficient, and cost-effective ways to perform integrity verification at large scale, incorporating recent advancements and improving existing SotA solutions.

Design of wireless communication systems based on machine learning enhancements

The **COLLABS** project will design anomaly detection blocks complementing IoT device channel estimation/localisation blocks based on deep learning at the network edge. Device channel estimation and/or device localisation will enable IoT device fingerprinting, producing learned models of device behaviour that will be used to generate device-specific signatures. In this way, anomalous device behaviour will be detectable through abrupt and/or unusual changes in devices' signal environment. Wireless fingerprinting-based methods will be integrated with IoT device remote attestation features, thus enabling the implementation of IoT device certification. This will help alleviate node forgery, identity spoofing, and related security problems. The work will be focused on wireless fingerprinting-based security for IoT devices in both the WiFi domain (e.g., IEEE 802.11 WiFi IoT standard) and mobile cellular IoT domain (3GPP NB-IoT or LTE-M).

3.2 Overview of research advances since March 2019

Distributed anomaly detection

Classical distance- and density-based unsupervised outlier detection approaches such as k-nearest neighbour (k-NN) distance and local outlier factor (LOF) have been used more rarely in industrial IoT applications compared to supervised and unsupervised model-based machine-learning and deep-learning methods. Recently, however, some works in this direction have appeared:

Zhu et al. (2020) proposed GAAOD, a k-NN-Based approximate outlier detection algorithm for IoT streaming data, which uses a grid-based index to manage summary information. Quek et al. (2020) introduced an approach for IoT load classification and anomaly warning in ELV DC Pico-grids, which employs hierarchical extended k-nearest neighbours and considers window blocks instead of individual data points in order to generate anomaly warnings.

Chamarajnar and Ashok (2019) employ the classical density-based LOF algorithm in order to identify integrity threats for distributed IoT systems in precision agriculture, while Garg et al. (2020) use the classical density-based clustering algorithm DBSCAN to build a multi-stage anomaly detection scheme for augmenting the security in general IoT-enabled applications.

Also, recently there appeared works on k-NN-based anomaly detection in related fields of wireless sensor networks (Wang et al., 2019) and general data streams (Wu et al., 2019).

Unsupervised machine/deep learning approaches to anomaly detection in IoT settings witnessed a recent proliferation of research activity, exemplified by the following works:

Bhatia et al. (2019) propose a network-centric, behaviour-learning based, anomaly detection approach for securing vulnerable IoT environments. The approach is centered around a model architecture which relies on deep autoencoders. Nguyen et al. (2019) present DIOT: a federated self-learning anomaly detection system for IoT which employs gated recurrent units (GRUs), a novel variant of recurrent neural networks (RNNs).

Diverging from deep learning, Shorman et al. (2019) describe an unsupervised intelligent system based on one class support vector machine (SVM) and grey wolf optimization for IoT botnet detection. An interesting approach to behavioural anomaly detection for IoT devices in enterprise networks was proposed by Yu et al. (2019), which is centered around finite-state machines.

Which unsupervised approach is better in IoT scenarios, classical distance- and density based methods or unsupervised machine/deep learning, seems to still be an open question. There exists a recent paper by Munir et al. (2019) which describes a comparative study of deep learning and traditional methods on streaming data, but since the experimental evaluation was performed on only two data sets (with only one giving an edge to deep learning), the results can be considered inconclusive in a more general sense, which includes industrial IoT applications.

Regarding supervised deep learning approaches, long short-term memory (LSTM) neural networks witnessed a recent surge in popularity. Wu et al. (2019) present an approach based on LSTM combined with Bayesian and Gaussian processing for anomaly detection in industrial IoT. Samani et al. (2020) also employ LSTM for anomaly detection in IoT-based passive infrared (PIR) occupancy sensors to improve building energy efficiency. Shukla and Sengupta (2020) combine LSTM with hierarchical clustering to implement outlier detection for two IoT application areas: vehicular traffic and air pollution.

As for traditional supervised machine learning approaches, Almaguer-Angeles et al. (2019) provide a comparative study involving a large number of algorithms for anomaly detection in smart building IoT scenarios.

Finally, distributed anomaly detection is explicitly investigated in several recent works. Ezeme et al. (2019) present a deep learning approach to distributed anomaly detection based on RNNs, introducing a multi-node ad-hoc network that uses a novel offloading scheme to bring an online anomaly detection capability to the nodes in the network. Müller et al. (2019) investigate distributed anomaly detection of single mote attacks in wireless sensor networks based on the RPL protocol, which relies on kernel density estimation.

Remote attestation

Recently researchers proposed different remote attestation schemes to address security issues in IIoT systems.

ESDRA. Kuang et al. (2019) proposed Efficient and Secure Distributed Remote Attestation (ESDRA), which aims to reduce the possibility of single node failure. In ESDRA, the network is divided into clusters based on the communication distance among nodes; one of the nodes within a cluster acts as a cluster-head. In ESDRA, every node is attested by three of its neighbours; the cluster head re-checks and sends the attestation report to the verifier.

EAPA. Yan et al. (2019) proposed a CRA scheme named Efficient Attestation scheme resilient to Physical Attacks. EAPA utilizes the mechanisms employing heartbeats. In this approach, every device in the network establishes a secure communication with its neighbour based on a secure key communication. Based on internal secure clock, every device generates a heartbeat and shares it with its neighbour. Upon receiving the heartbeats from the neighbours, every device authenticates the message and stores the result in a secure log.

SHeLA. Rabbani et al. (2019) proposed SHeLA, a scalable heterogeneous (i.e. a swarm that consists of nodes that communicate over different wireless communication protocols) layered attestation scheme for large IoT networks. The paper provides an architecture and a protocol for remote attestation of a swarm of IoT devices that considers the mobility of the provers. To this aim, the paper introduces an edge computing layer between the verifier and the swarm network. Multiple edge verifiers are deployed to cover different areas allowing swarm nodes to leave and join as needed. Each edge verifier also maintains information of every swarm registered, moved as guests, and all other Verifiers. The root Verifier has the information of all the other edge verifiers and swarm.

HEALED. Ibrahim et al. (2019) proposed HEaling and Attestation for Low-end Embedded Devices (HEALED). Authors claim that unlike other attestation mechanisms, HEALED not only detects malicious devices in a network, but also provides efficient mechanisms to disinfect the affected devices. The authors assume a network of low-end embedded devices where a set of devices act as verifiers and others set of devices as provers. Based on predefined time, the verifier attests the prover.

Given the goal of *COLLABS* to exploit state-of-the-art remote attestation solutions to strengthen security services (e.g., device attestation) of a large scale IIoT network; our objective is to develop novel, beyond state-of-the-art solutions. In particular the remote attestation literature does not provide solution where IoT devices communicate asynchronously (e.g., in Publish/subscribe setting). The ordering of events in an asynchronous environment is difficult. In *COLLABS* we will investigate this issue and provide solutions for distributed remote attestation which will secure IIoT devices that work in asynchronous environment. Moreover, remote attestation schemes do not provide solution for IoT systems that works in intermittent connectivity. As part of our goal in *COLLABS* we will deliver advanced mechanisms enabling *end-to-end security by design* in highly complex IoT environments. The innovative security concepts addressed in the project, such as SW integrity verification, secure SW updates, and HW-based authentication (i.e., as part of developed novel remote attestation scheme) will be *efficient and interoperable* to cope with IoT complexity, heterogeneity, and dynamicity in different industrial settings.

Design of wireless communication systems based on machine learning enhancements

Indoor positioning and tracking have attracted a fair amount of research attention recently. Belmonte-Hernández et al. (2019) presented SWiBluX, a complete indoor tracking system based on statistical fingerprinting and positioning based on deep learning, including an experimental evaluation which demonstrated the superiority of deep neural networks over traditional deterministic, probabilistic and machine-learning positioning methods. Chen et al. (2019) proposed an outlier immune multipath fingerprinting model for indoor single-site localization, employing the Binet-Cauchy kernel to map the multipath fingerprinting to a higher dimensional reproducing kernel Hilbert space. Zhang et al. (2019) tackle the problem of reducing the received signal strength (RSS) fingerprint database to a lower-rank matrix (low-dimensional space) using robust PCA, thus reducing the influence of noise and outliers on indoor localization.

The problem of resource allocation was also recently addressed using machine learning. Eisen et al. (2019) propose an approach for learning optimal resource allocations in wireless systems by handling stochastic constraints of functional optimization problems by training deep neural networks in dual domains. In a more specific scenario of large-scale wireless power allocation, Eisen and Ribeiro (2019) employ graph convolutional neural networks.

Optical Wireless Communication was explored by Lee et al. (2019), who propose a framework based on deep learning for optical wireless transceiver design.

Shi et al. (2019) present a multi-stage deep learning-based system for RF signal classification in unknown and dynamic spectrum environments, considering also the problems of outlier and jammer detection.

Moving on from practical application of the present or near future, Letaief et al. (2019) discuss a roadmap to 6G, and what they term “AI Empowered Wireless Networks”. The authors discuss potential technologies for 6G to enable mobile AI applications, as well as AI-enabled methodologies for 6G network design and optimization.

In the past year, a large number of relevant survey papers appeared, which, besides helping the realization of the *COLLABS* project, attest to the relevance, maturity, and fast-paced development of the field. Zhu et al. (2020) in “Toward an Intelligent Edge: Wireless Communication Meets Machine Learning” focus on the questions of leveraging the mobile edge as a computing platform and exploiting the massive data distributed over a large number of edge devices, as do Park et al. (2019) in their paper “Wireless Network Intelligence at the Edge”. Karunaratne and Gacanin (2019) present an overview of machine learning approaches in wireless mesh networks.

Sun et al. (2019) in “Application of Machine Learning in Wireless Networks: Key Techniques and Open Issues” focus on three aspects: resource management in the media access control (MAC) layer, networking and mobility management in the network layer, and localization in the application layer. Wang et al. (2020) present a comprehensive survey starting with the thirty-year history of machine learning, and investigating its use in various applications of wireless networks, including heterogeneous networks, cognitive radios, IoT, and machine to machine networks (M2M). The encyclopaedic survey by Zhang et al. (2019) focuses on deep learning and its applications within various aspects of mobile and wireless networking, from mobile data analysis to network control, security and applications.

Finally, Zappone et al. (2019) tackle in some sense a wider, in another sense a more specific problem of obtaining model-aided wireless artificial intelligence, by discussing methods for embedding expert knowledge in deep neural networks for wireless system optimization.

3.3 Overview of innovative commercial products released since March 2019

Anomaly Detection: The Environment for Developing KDD-Applications Supported by Index-Structures (ELKI) is a Java-based data-mining tool and API which implements many classical outlier detection algorithms (<https://elki-project.github.io/>). The most recent stable version 0.7.5 is dated February 15, 2019, with newer development versions available from the GitHub repository (<https://github.com/elki-project/elki>).

INTEL SGX: Intel Software Guard Extensions (Intel® SGX) provides hardware-based memory encryption to isolate specific application code and data in cloud and enterprise environments. Intel SGX offers a granular level of protection by allocating user-level code in the so-called enclaves which are private regions of memory designed to be protected from processes running at higher privilege levels. It is a secure architecture for resource-constrained, embedded systems that provide strong isolation guarantees, remote attestation, reliable communication, and deployment minimum secure hardware requirement. Intel SGX aims to provide a trust boundary which enables cloud providers to enhance the security of their services.

Intel SGX is also adopted by Intel Xeon E processors to guarantee hardware-based security consisting of CPU instructions and platform enhancements.

Between March 2019 and March 2020, four revisions of Intel SGX SDK have been released: 2.4, 2.5, 2.6 and 2.7. Besides various bug fixes and security enhancements, they include the following

major updates from previous versions: support for ECDSA based remote attestation, support for Intel AVX-512 instructions and Intel SHA Extensions New Instructions (SHA-NI) in trusted libraries, new memory allocation APIs, updated Local Attestation sample project, and improvements of the switchless library.

Machine Learning: For a brief overview of popular (distributed) ML tools, please see Section 8.3.

4 Physical security

4.1 Proposal's stated offering beyond March 2019 SotA

In the proposal of *COLLABS* we stated that our progress beyond the state-of-the art will be realized via two approaches. The first one will be showcasing that in terms of cost and complexity, the novel embedded security is a better alternative to classical solutions that solely rely on software; extending its applicability to large-scale deployments, thanks to the recent appearance of cheaper hardware solutions that do not compromise security (OPTIGA TPM/OPTIGA Trust).

The second approach will be to pioneer the demonstration of the existing synergies between physical security (hardware wallets), blockchain and IIoT applications.

In order to greatly increase European industrial efficiency in both secure asset tracking and secure multiparty transactions through smart contracts (e.g. introducing important savings in several operational costs like fraud and claims management) or escrow services, private credentials of thousands of devices must be individually safeguarded, in an efficient and highly secure way, so that blockchain becomes a real technological resource in IIoT.

The key enabler in this project is a novel physical security which must be standardised and certified to be credible, reliable and secure. At the same time, it should be cheap enough to be included in every device.

In the *COLLABS* project, IFAG's high-end state-of-the-art security chips (OPTIGA TPM 2.0) with highest security certification levels in the market will be extended by creating new drivers and high-level applications to showcase the applicability of the TPM2.0 standard API in novel applications, such as blockchain and IIoT. TPM will be adapted to new shields and evaluation boards so as to increase its application range and use in devices such as network gateways (e.g. Raspberry Pi based with Windows/Linux OS).

4.2 Overview of research advances since March 2019

Extremely robust security is paramount to assure a successful deployment of Industry 4.0 solutions in Europe. Current industrial IoT (IIoT) networks are either too expensive to maintain and deploy or lack adequate security levels, greatly harming the dissemination of Industry 4.0 in Europe. Through inexpensive and easy-to-use physical security, designed based on widely used and validated standards (TPM2.0, EAL4+, IETF RFC 6347), security can be assured without greatly compromising costs or hardening the user experience. Nevertheless, novel physical security devices are still not widely used, and market penetration is not optimal. They still lack testing and promotion in the IIoT market, since they are traditionally considered to be expensive and complex to use, not scalable enough to be individually embedded in networks potentially comprising thousands of devices. Similarly, their applicability in industrial blockchain applications is not yet demonstrated.

Research has started focusing on the related areas of cyber-physical systems security and industrial network security. Since March 2019, several papers were published in this context.

Standards for security and safety challenges for Industry 4.0 are examined and new solutions are presented by Kharchenko et al. (2019). The aim of this research is to enhance the conventional concepts of enterprise safety and security management by combining these two interrelated features in a single system.

Starting from a real-world use case, Frey et al. (2019) derived a security perspective for an information-centric industrial Internet of things. They analysed the potentials of information-centric networking for providing a secure and robust networking solution for constrained controllers in industrial safety systems.

To improve the trustworthiness of an industrial Internet of things network, Hassan et al. (2020) proposed a cyber-attack detection model, especially for detection of cyber-attack of Supervisory control and data acquisition (SCADA) by using the network traffics from SCADA based industrial Internet of things platform. This model uses industrial protocol-based network traffic.

Liu et al. (2019) studied a network security and data redundancy of the Cyber Physical System in industrial environment and proposed a trust-based active detection (TBAD) scheme.

Bienhaus et al. (2019) proposed a security architecture for gateway connecting production systems, such as sensors and actors, with cloud systems. The security architecture in this work is based on a Trusted Platform Module (TPM) 2.0.

Blockchain is a promising technology that along with other enablers can significantly improve security, transparency and peer-to-peer interaction at a lower cost and with less energy. Lee et al. (2019) propose a systematic blockchain based architecture to mitigate the inherent real-time implementation concerns of cyber physical systems in manufacturing application domain.

To simultaneously guarantee transaction efficiency and system security, Huang et al. (2019) have proposed a credit-based proof-of-work (PoW) mechanism for IIoT devices. The proposed mechanism is based on directed acyclic graph (DAG) structured blockchains which is further used to develop a data authority management method. This method regulates access to sensor data thereby protecting sensitive data confidentiality as well as data privacy.

The CHARIOT project (Loupos et al., 2019) is developing an innovative design method and cognitive platform that supports a unified and integrated approach towards data privacy, security and safety of industrial IoT systems including several technologies.

A recent Intel-sponsored book entitled “Demystifying IoT Security” contains a comprehensive chapter on IoT hardware security (Cheruvu et al., 2020). Attacks targeting hardware are increasing and are inherently complex. It is important to consider all the entry points in an IoT device life cycle (design, manufacturing, configuration, deployment, integration, management, dismissal). The chapter frames the need to enable end-2-end security covering (1) the edge area, where IoT devices (from sensors to controllers) are in operation, (2) the network infrastructure area, where multiple heterogeneous technologies are bridged by industrial gateways for integration with enterprise network, and (3) cloud-based services, allowing scalability and cross-organization interoperability. The chapter is focused on Intel product family and developed by Intel “Security Essentials” initiative. Despite this vendor-specific focus, the chapter provides a comprehensive overview of several foundational security capabilities that can be implemented at the CPU or SoC level: (1) device identity, (2) protected boot, (3) protected storage, (4) trusted execution environments, (5) built-in silicon security.

Moghimiet al. (2020) perform a black-box timing analysis of TPM 2.0 devices, revealing that some of these devices feature secret-dependent execution times during signature generation based on elliptic curves. In particular, they discovered timing leakage on an Intel firmware based TPM as well as a hardware TPM. By applying lattice techniques, it is possible to recover 256-bit private keys for ECDSA and ECSchnorr signatures, after about 1,300 observations and in less than two minutes. Similarly, they extract the private ECDSA key from a hardware TPM manufactured by STMicroelectronics, which is certified at Common Criteria (CC) EAL 4+, after fewer than 40,000 observations. They also demonstrate a remote attack against a StrongSwan

IPsec VPN that uses a TPM to generate the digital signatures for authentication. In this attack, the remote client recovers the server's private authentication key by timing only 45,000 authentication handshakes via a network connection. This shows the difficulty of correctly implementing known constant-time techniques, and the importance of testing and evaluation of cryptographic implementations.

Carreira et al. (May 2020) provide a comprehensive survey (Qualcomm, Trustonic, Huawei, Nvidia, and Linaro) on how different trusted execution environments (TEEs) are built on top of Arm TrustZone for the protection of security-critical applications and operating system components. TEEs are often assumed to be highly secure, relying on assumption on underlying TrustZone guarantees. In the paper the authors consider which types of vulnerabilities and limitations affect existing TrustZone-assisted TEE systems, what are the main challenges to build them correctly, and what contributions can be borrowed from the research community to overcome them.

Garlati and Pinto (2020) propose a new zero-trust computing architecture based on the concept of multi zone enclaves for RISC-V based Linux systems, thus providing support for TEEs at micro-architecture level. They achieve hardware-enforced software-defined boundaries with an extremely limited codebase (thus minimizing the attack surface), isolation of data segments and memory-mapped peripherals, isolation of interrupts, isolation of cores and other micro-architectural resources, strict time separation.

Wang and Stöttinger (2020) consider an automotive scenario, where hardware security modules are used to encrypt communications and authenticate devices in the networks. In those safety-critical scenarios encryption is essential, but it may become ineffective against quantum-enabled attackers. For this reason, the authors study the feasibility of employing quantum-resistant encryption schemes in the HSM, considering the ongoing work in NIST post-quantum cryptography initiative.

Going beyond the state-of-the-art, *COLLABS* will take into consideration these approaches and considerations and will propose an ideal solution for large-scale industrial deployments that require a high-level of security with minimal performance overheads.

4.3 Overview of innovative commercial products released since March 2019

Nordic Semiconductors has a wide range of low-power, wireless, high-security SoC for Industry 4.0 applications¹¹ in sensing, remote control and robotics. On mid-range devices Nordic integrates **ARM** security ecosystem, including multiple security hardware-IPs:

- Processor IPs¹² supporting TrustZone for software isolation, physical tampering and memory protection
- CryptoIsland¹³, supporting management of cybersecurity of the device in its lifetime, dedicated crypto-capabilities (ciphering, hashing, TRNG) for isolation and hardware acceleration, software integrity attestation; also providing high protection against a number of physical attacks (including power and electromagnetic side-channel analysis)¹⁴
- CryptoCell¹⁵ supporting security in high-efficiency systems with a small footprint and low power consumption, and offering platform security and cryptographic services.

¹¹ <https://www.nordicsemi.com/Applications/Industrial-automation>

¹² <https://www.arm.com/products/silicon-ip-cpu/cortex-m/cortex-m35p>

¹³ <https://www.arm.com/products/silicon-ip-security/cryptoisland>

¹⁴ <https://www.arm.com/products/silicon-ip-security/side-channel-mitigation>

¹⁵ <https://www.arm.com/products/silicon-ip-security/crypto-cell-300>

CryptoCell complements TrustZone for Armv8-M, and together they form a secure processing environment, to isolate sensitive assets and processes from potentially malicious application code.

Nordic in November 2019¹⁶ announced a new family of products, the nRF5, among which there is the nRF5340TM mid-range system-on-chip, with dual-processor hardware architecture low-power and short-range wireless connectivity, and integrated ARM-Cryptocell, TrustZone, and secure key storage. These integrated solutions provide the advantage of having a cohesive and transparent ecosystem, with SW and platforms hiding a lot of complexity. For smart home applications, Nordic is also developing a partnership with Amazon¹⁷ to integrate their devices into Amazon Common Software integration platform¹⁸. These are very convenient ecosystems and will constitute a valid option in the future. However, for Industry 4.0 applications we see strong limitations in applicability to infrastructures with heterogeneous technologies and vendors, and where legacy equipment has a very long lifetime.

STMicroelectronics takes another approach, by developing a family of secure MCUs, certified as per the latest security standards (Common Criteria EAL6+, BSI certification, EMVCo, CUP) and covering several interfaces for integration in existing embedded platforms.

- STSAFE-TPM family offers a trusted computing solution, which provides platform integrity, secret storage, and signature generation services for Windows/Linux devices.
- STSAFE-A is an optimized secure element offering authentication and data protection services, such as transport layer security (TLS) session establishment, covering brand protection use cases, for connected and non-connected objects.
- STSAFE-J is a flexible, Java-based secure element that can either embed a default or application-specific ST applet, as it is the case for smart grids, or customer-built applet.

ST announced in May 2019¹⁹ a next generation mixed signals MCU family STM32G4, targeting industrial appliances, with embedded security measures to protect memory access for secure storage, to support secure live firmware upgrade, to disable debugging functions after programming for attack-surface reduction, to provide hardware AES-256 encryption and TRNG. This latter solution falls back to an approach that requires replacing legacy equipment with new one, but no common approach has been established in Europe to support industries and equipment providers in the process.

NXP offers a combination of hardware and trusted firmware solutions which can be used as root of trust to create trusted systems²⁰. In June 2019²¹ NXP announced a new Plug & Trust Secure Element Family to secure Industry 4.0 and Internet of things (IoT) applications (from edge to cloud), with Common Criteria (CC) EAL 6+ certification. EdgeLock simplifies the implementation of high-performance security for sensing and control. Key features of this solution are listed below:

- 4096 bits RSA cryptography and integration of elliptic curve (ECC) cryptography
- SDK and applets to minimize the need to write security code, scalable software platform

¹⁶<https://www.nordicsemi.com/News/2019/11/Nordic-unveils-worlds-first-dual-Arm-Cortex-M33-processor-wireless-SoC-nRF5340>

¹⁷<https://www.nordicsemi.com/News/2020/02/Nordic-announces-support-for-Amazon-Common-Software-for-Devices>

¹⁸<https://developer.amazon.com/acs-devices>

¹⁹https://www.st.com/content/st_com/en/about/media-center/press-item.html/p4159.html

²⁰https://www.nxp.com/applications/solutions/communication-infrastructure/network-security-technology/trusted-systems-technology:NETWORK_SECURITY_INT_SEC

²¹<https://media.nxp.com/news-releases/news-release-details/nxp-edglock-se050-plug-trust-secure-element-family-provides>

- Norms compliance: claimed to support compliance to National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), International Society of Automation Industrial Network and System Security IEC62443, OPC Industrial Interoperability Standard for Unified Architecture (OPC UA), and the Open Connectivity Foundation (OFC) specification
- Support to deployment of IoT services and integration in a Cloud-based infrastructure
 - o Master/slave communication solutions for direct control of critical functions as well as integrity and confidentiality of sensor data
 - o Measures for secure parameter configuration update
 - o Integration of trusted platform modules (TPM), combining into a unique solution security of IoT connections, as well as IoT platform integrity and attestation
 - o Support to integration with different microcontrollers, microprocessors, operating systems (Linux, RTOS, Windows, Android) and major cloud platforms

This solution from NXP seems to cover a broad range of devices (from sensing to control and communications) and to address the challenges of integration of secure solutions into novel Industry 4.0 infrastructures (edge/cloud) with adequate support for scalability.

Maxim has multiple solutions for hardware security²²:

- DeepCover Security Managers, can be integrated with existing microcontrollers to provide data protection through on-chip non-imprinting memory and physical tamper protection
- DeepCover Authenticators, to implement parts and devices authentication
- Secure Microcontrollers, providing hardware cryptographic engines, physical layer security for side-channel protection, integrated secure memory, secure boot support

In February 2020 Maxim announced MAX32520 ChipDNA²³, the first ARM Cortex M4-based secure microcontroller with built-in physically unclonable function (PUF) technology for financial- and government-grade security. Maxim's Integrated PUF technology allows for multiple layers of protection to provide the most advanced key-protection technology in a cost-effective format for use in IoT, healthcare, industrial and computing systems. The microcontroller supports secret keys storage with physical attacks protection, IP protection through PUF based encryption, NIST SP 800-90A/B compliant TRNG, hardware acceleration for AES-256, ECDSA P-521, SHA-512. Such a solution supports incorporation of very advanced security features in existing platforms.

Microchip has a family of products dedicated to introducing advanced security features in embedded platforms²⁴. These products cover different areas:

- Security focused ICs, providing key protection, secure authentication, segregated crypto-primitives supporting acceleration, integration in the Trust Platform (more info below)
- MCUs with advanced security capabilities, including crypto-engines, ARM TrustZone for partitioning, full TLS/WiFi stack implemented in hardware, hardware root of trust, lifecycle management

In September 2019 Microchip announced its Trust Platform²⁵, which leverages the CryptoAuthentication product family to simplify and develop IoT devices authentication at scale

²² <https://www.maximintegrated.com/en/products/embedded-security.html>

²³ https://www.maximintegrated.com/en/aboutus/newsroom.html/pr_245588699

²⁴ <https://www.microchip.com/design-centers/embedded-security>

²⁵ <https://www.microchip.com/pressreleasepage/microchip-simplifies-hardware-based-iot-security-trust-platform>

with a pre-provisioned solution. The Trust Platform is structured into three-tiers: (1) the first tier (Trust & Go) provides zero-configuration secure elements for automated cloud or LoRaWAN authentication on-boarding leveraging Microchip as a certificate authority, (2) the second tier (TrustFLEX) provides support to integrate client's specific certificate authority with pre-configured use-cases such as TLS-hardened communication, secure boot, OTS-updates, and key updates, (3) the third tier (TrustCOM) provides full control to implement customer-specific provisioning and integration of customer-specific applications. Further simplification of IoT authentication deployment has been introduced through collaboration with Amazon Web Services, to implement a simplified onboarding process on AWS IoTservices²⁶.

Infineon has a different approach looking towards the hardware security module (HSM), additional hardware to the microprocessor of general use which is in charge of all the elements belonging to the field of cybersecurity:

- Secure authentication, encryption with algorithms with symmetric key (blowfish, AES) and asymmetric key (RSA, ECC), protecting the boot process, protecting the IP, protection from updates, secure store of store valuable data.
- Infineon's technology is safe against tamper physical attacks, timing attacks and side-channels attack.

In December 2019, the Optiga Trust M SLS32AIA²⁷ was announced by Infineon. The OPTIGA Trust M is a high-end security solution that provides an anchor of trust for connecting IoT devices to the cloud, giving every IoT device its own unique identity. This pre-personalized turnkey solution offers secured, zero-touch onboarding and the high performance needed for quick cloud access. This product offers secure data storage and key provisioning, protection against tamper physics attack, a secure execution of the most important cryptographic algorithms and TRNG.

²⁶ <https://www.microchip.com/design-centers/security-ics/cryptoauthentication/cloud-authentication/aws-iot-atecc608a>

²⁷ <https://www.infineon.com/cms/en/product/security-smart-card-solutions/optiga-embedded-security-solutions/optiga-trust/optiga-trust-m-sls32aia/>

5 Function as a service (FaaS)

5.1 Proposal's stated offering beyond March 2019 SotA

Function as a service (FaaS), also referred to as “serverless computing”, describes an event-driven computing model that enables users to specify a function to be run, while abstracting the complexity of the necessary infrastructure to the function provider. FaaS typically follows a pay per use model where users are charged for the function runtime only. This computing model is inherently scalable allowing functions to scale automatically (e.g., during peak times) and independently with usage, but with a trade-off in latency.

To further clarify the positioning of FaaS in comparison to other cloud computational paradigms that are typically employed nowadays please refer to Figure 4.

Figure 4: FaaS in comparison with other cloud computing paradigms. [Source: <https://serverless.zone>]

While the increased abstraction that FaaS adopts minimised security management of the underlying layers (e.g., at the infrastructure level), function owners still have to consider the security of the data that their applications rely upon, and which is often shared between applications of different owners and/or trust domains.

COLLABS innovation beyond the state-of-the-art: To meet industry needs, **COLLABS** will elaborate on how to combine the FaaS computing model with methods for computing on encrypted data.

The project will leverage technologies to run joint analytics and machine learning algorithms on shared data while preserving requirements regarding data access regulations and data privacy. While there are several implementations for secure multiparty computation (SMC)²⁸ and homomorphic encryption (HE)²⁹ protocols available that allow secure and privacy-preserving calculations on shared datasets, existing solutions are currently rather tailored to the needs of specific use cases than providing a more generic solution in order allow secure computing on

²⁸ SMC allows separate parties to perform joint computations while keeping their inputs private from one another.

²⁹ Sophisticated cryptographic protection allowing manipulation of data without a need to decrypt it first.

shared data. These solutions in general show lower performance and efficiency compared to computation on plaintext data and do not provide the required levels of scalability, reliability, and elasticity that is required for big data applications in an industrial environment.

Considering the above, *COLLABS* will come up with a concept and a TRL 7 solution to demonstrate how the mentioned technologies can be used in the production cycle and evaluate both implementation security and the applicability in industrial environments.

5.2 Overview of research advances since March 2019

Secure processing of data, without revealing its content to the involved parties, is in the research limelight, as complex workflows involving parties that are not fully trusted or operate in different trust domains are typical in IoT and cloud-based computing infrastructures. The importance of these technologies has also increased considering recent developments in the privacy regulatory landscape, through the introduction of legislations such as GDPR, which dictate that data controllers and processors strictly limit access to the private-sensitive data they handle, providing sufficient guarantees to ensure the protection of the rights of the data subject.

In the context of secure multiparty computations, researchers have recently proposed novel computation protocols (e.g., based on one-way functions where each party sends two hardware-generated tokens to every other part (Badrinarayanan et al., Nov 2019)), but have also proposed leveraging the multiparty computation concept for enhancing the security and privacy of other technologies currently receiving a lot of attention, such as for distributed ledger technologies (DLTs), and Hyperledger Fabric in specific (Benhamouda et al., Apr 2019), as well as for machine learning applications (Chandran et al., Feb 2019).

Research on homomorphic encryption continues as well, with novel approaches being proposed by researchers, such as studying and improving upon the security (Xu et al., May 2019) or noise growth (Costache, et al., May 2019) of the algorithms. A significant body of recent work aims to overcome the performance and scalability limitations of homomorphic encryption, proposing approaches leveraging purpose-built hardware parallel architectures (Roy, et al., Feb 2019), the trusted computing paradigm (Wang, et al., May 2019), as well as improved homomorphic encryption -based algorithms for typical tasks such as classification (Xiao, et al., Oct 2019). As is the case with multiparty computations above, novel works have also focused on the use of homomorphic encryption in a number of key applications, such as secret sharing (Boyle, et al., Apr 2019), and DLT-based accountability mechanisms (Xu, et al., Feb 2020).

5.3 Overview of innovative commercial products released since March 2019

Various products have recently entered the market since the domain of platforms enabling FaaS secure data processing, as well as that of products enabling the secure processing of data, are flourishing. Some interesting solutions identified are detailed below.

Enveil – Homomorphic encryption

Enveil³⁰ is a pioneering data security company protecting Data in Use to enable secure search, analytics, sharing, and collaboration (see Figure 5). Founded by U.S. Intelligence Community alumni with backgrounds in mathematics, algorithmics, and machine learning, Enveil is revolutionizing data security by addressing the Data in Use vulnerability that people have been chasing for more than 20 years.

³⁰ <https://www.enveil.com/>

Figure 5. The Enveil security solution. [Source: <https://www.enveil.com/>]

Inpher – Secure multiparty computation

Inpher's³¹ XOR Secret Computing® Engine (or XOR, for short — pronounced 'ex-or') is built from proprietary advances in *secure multiparty computation*. Leveraging encryption in-use technologies, XOR securely distributes a computation across multiple parties where no individual party can see the other parties' data during the process (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Secret Computing concept. [Source: <https://www.inpher.io/>]

³¹ <https://www.inpher.io/>

Cybernetica – Sharemind secure analytics

Cybernetica's Sharemind³² data analysis system (see Figure 7) is targeted at secure processing confidential information. The solution is based on secure data sharing as well as secure multi-party computations, allowing data analytics to securely process confidential information.

Figure 7. Cybernetica Sharemind secure analytics. [Source: <https://cyber.ee/>]

In more detail, the data is encrypted on-site by data owners and uploaded to Sharemind cloud servers. Data analysts can build and run queries on such data (e.g., to gain insights and detect patterns), without accessing the data itself, since Sharemind processes the queries at the cloud without removing the data protection. The results are presented to the data analysts in an encrypted format, accessible only by authorised users, while all computations and results follow set policies and are fully auditable.

Duality - SecurePlus Platform

The Duality SecurePlus Platform³³ (see Figure 8) is a secure computing platform focusing on enabling organizations to deploy advanced AI and analytics on encrypted data. Privacy is preserved throughout the analytics cycle through the use of homomorphic encryption to protect both data and models.

Figure 8. Duality SecurePlus Platform. [Source: <https://dualitytech.com/>]

³² <https://cyber.ee/products/secure-analytics/>

³³ <https://dualitytech.com/duality-secureplus-platform/>

Duality is based on the PALISADE³⁴ homomorphic encryption library, which is a portable, open-source library providing efficient implementations of lattice cryptography and homomorphic encryption schemes. It should be noted that PALISADE follows the HomomorphicEncryption.org security standards for homomorphic encryption (more on that below).

Big Industry FaaS Solutions

A number of FaaS solutions are already available in the market, since all major cloud players offer a “serverless computing” service scheme. Some key offerings in the field are listed below, with updates and improvements to the various offerings being constantly introduced (cloud computing, and FaaS in specific, being a very competitive market):

- AWS Lambda³⁵
 - o Updates to an already existing commercial FaaS solution by Amazon
- OpenFaaS³⁶
 - o Updates to an already existing open source FaaS solution
- Microsoft Azure Functions³⁷
 - o Updates to an already existing commercial FaaS solution by Microsoft
- Google Firebase³⁸
 - o Updates to an already existing commercial FaaS solution backed by Google
- IBM Cloud Functions³⁹
 - o Updates to an already existing commercial FaaS solution from IBM based on Apache OpenWhisk

Related Initiatives and Alliances

A couple of noteworthy initiatives have been identified that aim to enable the wider adoption and standardisation of homomorphic encryption and multi-party computations. These are:

- HomomorphicEncryption.org⁴⁰
 - o An open consortium of industry, government and academia aiming to standardize homomorphic encryption. Members include prominent industry stakeholders (e.g., Google, Intel, Microsoft, Samsung, Mastercard, IBM), government stakeholders (e.g., NIST, ITU) and academia (e.g., Columbia, MIT, EPFL), who are all working towards developing a community standard for homomorphic encryption.
- MPC Alliance⁴¹
 - o A group of industry companies with strong roots in academia, aiming to accelerate the adoption of MPC. The alliance offers help with cross-industry education and exploration of the potential of MPC in a number of use cases, being open to companies who may not already use MPC, but recognize its potential as an important technological tool.

³⁴ <https://palisade-crypto.org/>

³⁵ <https://aws.amazon.com/lambda/>

³⁶ <https://www.openfaas.com/>

³⁷ <https://azure.microsoft.com/en-us/services/functions/>

³⁸ <https://firebase.google.com/>

³⁹ <https://cloud.ibm.com/functions/>

⁴⁰ <https://homomorphicencryption.org/>

⁴¹ <https://www.mpcalliance.org/>

6 Secure and trusted execution environments

6.1 Proposal's stated offering beyond March 2019 SotA

With the recent proliferation of Trusted Execution Environments (TEEs) such as ARM TrustZone⁴² and Intel SGX⁴³, a number of cloud providers plan to introduce TEE capabilities within their premises. The embedding of TEEs within the cloud allows the design of secure applications that can tolerate malware and system vulnerabilities, as application-specific secrets are shielded from any privileged code on the same host. As such, TEEs have pushed innovation in the area of secure computation, with an increasing number of proposals that promote TEE-based applications in the cloud (for example, Krawiecka et al., 2017). Even though the community features a number of studies on SGX security in the cloud, no previous work has addressed the problem of enabling cloud services to offer distributed applications over SGX, as the specific environment paradigm is currently designed to serve centralised applications.

Furthermore, hardware platforms are not immune to bugs that may be exploited by adversaries to compromise the TEE. Therefore, even at a local node level, devices of critical systems also require additional layers of system hardening and remote protection mechanisms. Remote attestation is a well-known technique for verifying the state of remote computing devices and for verifying the trustworthiness of the data collected and shared by remote sensors. It is well-suited for IoT and can provide benefit to a broad range of IoT-like applications that involve sensors, but it is not trivial to integrate into IoT devices (Abera et al., 2016). To provide security at the application interface, some works have started recently to utilise the ARM TrustZone, which can enable TEEs. However, it does not provide memory encryption, hence data disclosure attacks are still possible. Also, the majority of these solutions often disregard the real-time needs of the IoT applications.

COLLABS innovation beyond the state-of-the-art: As industry moves towards cloud deployment of critical applications in order to take advantage of the high availability and effective resource utilization that it offers, **COLLABS** aims to design, evaluate and deploy frameworks that will allow distributed, elastic applications to run securely in such environments. This will be accomplished by leveraging the security provisions of the SGX trusted execution environment that to this day have only been offered to centralized applications.

To further improve the security at both local and cloud level, **COLLABS** will be built upon the assumption that trusted execution environments are also prone to attacks as hardware (or firmware) level bugs may be present. Current trust application models that leverage TEEs like SGX, include the trusted execution environment in the trusted code base, thus failing to account for compromise of the SGX platform and their security provisions fall short in such cases. **COLLABS** will utilise subversion-resilient cryptographic techniques (Bellare et al., 2014) to design a framework that leverages SGX for security provisioning but, at the same time, accounts for possible hardware compromise and provides concrete security guarantees, thereby refining the common threat model of SGX-based applications. **COLLABS** will explore more trusted execution environments which can enable remote attestation and additionally provide full memory encryption.

Focusing on local or edge devices, **COLLABS** aims to revisit the existing and well-known system hardening techniques (that have effectively been applied to desktop and server systems)

⁴² <https://developer.arm.com/ip-products/security-ip/trustzone>

⁴³ <https://software.intel.com/en-us/sgx>

and adapt them to the requirements of resource-constrained IoT devices, thus formally protecting them from advanced code injection and modification attacks. Furthermore, for real industrial IoT deployments, the assumption that an adversary cannot have physical access is not a valid one. Most state-of-the-art remote attestation techniques exclude such adversarial assumptions and as such *COLLABS*' ambition is to develop a remote attestation technique which will be effective even in the case of a hardware attack and inform the network owner the possible presence of a hardware attacker.

6.2 Overview of research advances since March 2019

Research on security of trusted execution environments or applications using TEEs is very active as the security requirements of both industry and end-users increase with the number of networked devices that cover all aspects of activity and the wide deployment of applications and services in the cloud. As such, a significant number of research works has been published in the past year (March 2019 to March 2020) and an overview of the most relevant ones to *COLLABS* will be attempted.

With the proliferation of cloud and distributed applications, it is natural that researchers look into tapping the increased security that can be achieved by deploying trusted applications in TEEs. One of the most widely spread distributed application domains is blockchain smart contracts and cryptocurrency transactions. Hardjono and Smith (2019) propose and lay the foundations for decentralized trusted computing base as an extension of the trusted computing base (TCB) concept. In their proposal, they identify the benefits of using Root-of-Trust systems such as Intel's SGX however they notice that those currently available do not consider their role in establishing a decentralized TCB (DTCB). For DTCB establishment, the authors propose that a group of TCB nodes must cooperatively verify that potential DTCB member nodes' TCB trust properties are aligned with vetted DTCB policies. Moving forward in virtualized cloud environments, a TCB layered approach using SGX TCB architecture at specific layers is proposed.

Realizing the limitations of centralized applications, a distributed cryptocurrency exchange using trusted hardware is proposed by Bentov et al. (2019). The service that the authors propose relies on TEE and their reference implementation uses SGX in order to perform within-enclave blockchain monitoring to prevent eclipse attacks while also using a consensus group of TEE-backed nodes that can enforce and/or cancel transactions in the case that the main (asset-holding) exchange node becomes unavailable.

While the aforementioned applications represent typical examples of modern high-profile decentralized applications, there are many traditional applications that are moving to cloud infrastructure in the form of a virtualized environment (deployed in a virtual machine, a container or even a network function). Researchers demonstrate that TEEs can effectively be used to strengthen the security of those solutions by adopting either Intel's SGX or ARM's TrustZone solutions (Sechkova et al., 2019) or developing purely open-source frameworks (Jin et al., 2019).

Besides securing an application, protecting user data and privacy becomes an additional design parameter, especially as deploying applications on the cloud involves transferring sensitive information to system infrastructure that the end user or the service provider may not control. Deyannis et al. (2020) demonstrate that TEEs can be used to implement a malware analysis application in a remote server. Their application is executed entirely in secure enclaves shielding the transfer and processing of user data in an environment that is potentially untrusted.

It should be noted that most of the works presented above, in spite of using commercially available TEEs, do not take their security for granted. This is an approach that **COLLABS** also follows by considering that hardware TEEs can be compromised. This seems to be an important and valid assumption, as research on attacks on these systems proves. In the past couple of years, a number of vulnerabilities have been uncovered that attack the secure enclaves or are able to compromise the security and management engines and therefore destroy the root-of-trust. While some of the earlier attacks such as Foreshadow (Van Bulck et al., 2018) have been partially mitigated⁴⁴, others keep surfacing, and the mitigations offered present a significant performance penalty and may require replacing CPUs for full protection. The following represent a list of attacks targeting Intel's SGX that have been disclosed within 2019 and up to March 2020:

- Enclave attack (Schwarz et al., 2019)
- MicroScope replay attack (Skarlatos et al., 2019)
- Plundervolt⁴⁵ (2019)
- Load Value Injection (LVI)⁴⁶ (2020)

It should be noted that other commercial TEEs such as ARM's TrustZone are not immune to vulnerabilities and indeed several attacks on such systems have been disclosed. Recent disclosures of such attacks include VoltJockey (Qiu et al., 2019) and a survey on vulnerabilities on TrustZone-assisted systems by Cerdeira et al. (May 2020) already discussed in Section 4.2.

6.3 Overview of innovative commercial products released since March 2019

In addition to the active research on TEEs, the industry is also moving rapidly in the domain by offering new solutions, standards and proposed practices. For mobile devices in the IoT or edge space, Trusty⁴⁷ has been released in December 2019 in order to support the TEEs on Tegra and other devices employing Android and TrustZone-based TEE. The project is available as open-source and provided as part of the Android Open Source Project (AOSP).

Another entirely open-source approach is Keystone⁴⁸ (Song et al., 2020). It is an open-source project for building TEEs with secure hardware enclaves, based on the RISC-V architecture, with a goal to build a secure and trustworthy open-source secure hardware enclave, accessible to everyone in industry and academia. Keystone introduces customizable TEE, a new paradigm of building TEE wherein both platform providers and enclave developers customize their TEE to have minimal trusted computing base (TCB), and is highly optimized for the resource usage of each application. This enables a lot of use cases of Keystone enclaves from embedded IoT application to machine learning.

In 2019, an industry-wide consortium, the Confidential Computing Consortium⁴⁹, including members such as Microsoft, Intel, ARM, IBM, RedHat, Tencent, Alibaba Cloud, Baidu and Google Cloud and operating under Linux Foundation's umbrella has been formed. The stated goal is to define and accelerate the adoption of confidential computing. Confidential computing focuses on securing data in use. Current approaches to securing data often address data at rest (storage) and in transit (network) but encrypting data in use is possibly the most challenging step

⁴⁴ <https://newsroom.intel.com/editorials/protecting-our-customers-through-lifecycle-security-threats/>

⁴⁵ <https://www.rambus.com/blogs/plundervolt-steals-keys-from-cryptographic-algorithms/>

⁴⁶ <https://lviattack.eu/>

⁴⁷ <https://docs.nvidia.com/jetson/l4t/index.html#page/Tegra%20Linux%20Driver%20Package%20Development%20Guide/trusty.html>

⁴⁸ <https://keystone-enclave.org/>

⁴⁹ <https://confidentialcomputing.io/>

to providing a fully encrypted lifecycle for sensitive data. Confidential computing will enable encrypted data to be processed in memory without exposing it to the rest of the system and reduce exposure for sensitive data and provide greater control and transparency for users. The project leverages secure hardware architectures (namely Intel's SGX and ARM's TrustZone for both Linux and Windows operating systems) and provides an open source framework (Open Enclave SDK⁵⁰) that allows developers to build TEE applications using a single enclaving abstraction. Developers can build applications once that run across multiple TEE architectures.

⁵⁰ <https://openenclave.io/sdk/>

7 Encrypted traffic analysis

7.1 Proposal's stated offering beyond March 2019 SotA

Encrypted network traffic has been steadily growing in volume in recent years, compared to nonencrypted traffic. This presents a challenge to the task of acquiring insight into the nature of the traffic, since network packet payload contents are not visible.

Traditional network traffic analysis techniques use machine learning (usually deep learning) methods to identify patterns in network flows. Deep packet inspection (DPI) systems for detecting anomalies or abnormal activities can identify attacks against ICS networks in a proactive manner, reporting any suspicious activities. A major disadvantage of such systems is their focus on clear-text packet payloads only. Taking into account the proliferation of encrypted network traffic, such approaches are bound to become obsolete. For this reason, techniques for network traffic analysis need to focus on detecting patterns in network flows based on metadata found in packet headers, such as packet lengths, timestamps, directions and inter-arrival times.

There exist works which attempt to solve various encrypted network traffic analysis problems, including identification of Web pages transferred over encrypted tunnels established by privacy enhancing technologies, mobile application classification, identification of fine-grained events (like messaging) at application-level, or privacy leaks originating from mobile applications (Enck et al., 2014). In the field of malware detection, it was established that encrypted malware traffic can be detected using contextual flow data, such as TLS handshake metadata (Anderson and McGrew, 2016). There are also works that successfully generate network signatures by discovering the underlying encryption algorithms and keys (De Carli et al., 2017).

COLLABS innovation beyond the state-of-the-art: The *COLLABS* project aims to design a system that will analyse encrypted network traffic, specifically to identify malicious behaviour which hides its identity under encrypted streams. To achieve this goal, as a first step the project will incorporate known techniques in the literature focusing on metadata extraction – without paying the high cost of decryption – and applying them to the task of malicious behaviour detection. The outcome of this step will provide insight on proper approaches to metadata handling and processing in order to produce network signatures that will be used to enrich current network inspection systems' functionality. In the training stages of machine learning, ground-truth datasets of malicious traffic need to be collected and analysed to derive signatures based on traffic metadata. The obtained signatures will be then integrated into the network inspection system to report possible attacks or traffic anomalies inside real network traffic.

7.2 Overview of research advances since March 2019

There has been a breadth of research on the analysis of encrypted network traffic (Apthorpe et al., 2017; Sirinam et al., 2018; Reed and Kranch, 2017). Currently, network data are generally encrypted as non-encrypted traffic that can be subject to a broad range of attacks. Such attacks vary from impersonation attack, man in the middle attacks to false data injection attacks. Moreover, attacker models could be both honest and curious, as well as malicious adversaries violating user anonymity. Even if the messages are encrypted, traffic analysis can be used to infer sensitive information from the packet characteristics such as timing patterns, sizes, and packet rates. Furthermore, it can be used to find correlations between input and output links of a network to reveal connections between the links. One typical measure is to perform network traffic monitoring as well as guaranteeing security and privacy for user data and systems. In

order to identify specific user behaviours, one way is to analyse the features and characteristics of traffic flows including encrypted traffic flows.

In the following, we highlight the major works related to analysing encrypted traffic across a variety of applications and settings such as IoT device fingerprinting, web fingerprinting, voice command attacks, VoIP traffic analysis, encrypted video stream analysis.

Msadek et al. (2019) demonstrate that an attacker is able to disclose sensitive information (user behaviour) about the IoT device by identifying specific patterns in IoT traffic. To do that, the authors train machine learning algorithms based on selected features extracted from the encrypted IoT traffic. In order to perform the fingerprint attack, the authors implement and simulate their approach. One work has been dedicated to Internet of things devices includes the Amazon Echo. Noah Apthorpe et al. (2019) observed the send/receive rates of SSL network traffic between the Amazon Echo and the IP address associated with an Amazon server. They observed that certain spikes in send/receive rates could be used by an attacker to interfere the content of the user's interactions with the Amazon Echo.

In order to detect the status of drones for instance flying or lying on the ground, Sciancalepore et al. (2019) propose a technique to detect the current status of drones, leveraging the communication traffic exchanged between the drone and its remote controller. The technique applies standard classification algorithms to the eavesdropped traffic analysing features such as packet size and packets inter-arrival time.

In the context of voice command fingerprinting, Kennedy et al. (2019) use different attack algorithms commonly used in website fingerprinting have been adapted to the voice command fingerprinting setting. The performing attack was able to correctly infer a voice command with an accuracy of 33.8%.

Rahman, et al. (2019) examined the burst level timing features including packet timestamps, time variances, and other time-based features of the encrypted traffic bursts. They evaluated this feature set by using several different fingerprinting attacks and showed that the performance of the attack increased when using both packet direction and timing features.

Attacks on encrypted voice over IP (VoIP) calls are related to voice command fingerprinting since in both attack scenarios an adversary is attempting to infer the content of encrypted network traffic with audio data included in the payload. Wang et al. (2005) proposed an attack which tracks Skype calls placed through an anonymous network by using timing metadata of the VoIP flow. Then, Soltani et al. (2020) analysed the fundamental limits of invisible flow fingerprinting.

Another research thread is the fingerprinting of encrypted video streams in order to infer the context of encrypted video stream based on its network traffic. Schuster et al. (2017) use CNNs to identify patterns in the encrypted network traffic that reveal the content of the video stream. Mitra et al. (2019) study the leakage sensitive information from interactive Netflix movies using encrypted traffic analysis. Even though Netflix uses end-to-end encryption from information leaking to unauthorized parties, however encrypted network traffic analysis demonstrate that they could infer basic information about the preferences of Netflix viewers. The authors present a traffic analysis technique for interactive video that can leak more information than non-interactive videos.

Finally, malware detection in encrypted data traffic has attracted research attention recently. De Lucia and Cotton (2019) propose a malicious communication detection mechanism over the transport layer security (TLS) protocol using support vector machines (SVM) and, alternatively, CNNs. Bazuhair and Lee (2020) enhance the CNN model in order to effectively detect malicious encrypted network traffic by using Perlin noise. Liu et al. (2019) present a distance-based

method for malware detection which employs the XGBoost algorithm on top of distances inferred using Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM) and Ordering Points To Identify the Clustering Structure (OPTICS) clustering techniques.

The above-mentioned works provide additional motivation for establishing a robust, systematic and comprehensive approach to anomaly detection in encrypted network data within the COLLABS framework.

7.3 Overview of innovative commercial products released since March 2019

Network traffic is increasing at an unprecedented pace. In our current landscape a significant amount of data is generated and exchanged through mobile and Internet of things (IoT) devices, such as those found in smart homes and smart cities. There are corresponding security and privacy risks and challenges associated with such a trend. According to Gartner, by 2019, 80% of all traffic was encrypted and most of network attacks (70%) could take advantage of encrypted traffic. Therefore, IoT vendors need to secure the traffic and devices they bring to market.

Blake Anderson Advanced security research group of CISCO presents a work about the “Network visibility and security analytics: Cisco Stealthwatch release 6.9.2” (CISCO, 2020). In particular, the “Encrypted traffic analytics” is a technology of CISCO that leverages a dedicated ASIC architecture to extract the data elements without slowing the data network. This approach is passed to Stealthwatch in order to apply various analytics technique to detect malware.

8 AI-enabled cybersecurity in IIoT-based collaborative manufacturing environments

8.1 Proposal's stated offering beyond March 2019 SotA

artificial intelligence (AI) is a vast field that has been proven to be crucial for cybersecurity. neural networks in general and recurrent neural networks (RNN) in particular have found wide applications due to their effectiveness in handling noisy, fast-flowing and heterogeneous data streams gathered from distributed sensors. On the other hand, randomised neural networks and especially reservoir computing (RC) models provide a state-of-the-art trade-off between efficiency and effectiveness in solving temporal learning tasks, allowing to embed learning functionalities even on low power devices. The application of AI in intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDPS) reduces false positives and increases accuracy, at the same time learning to understand new threats. Deep learning (DL) research demonstrated that accuracy can be further improved through use of deep belief networks. However, DL is positioned at another end of the spectrum with respect to RC efficiency, being an ML approach requiring considerable computational, communication and storage resources to produce effective results.

COLLABS innovation beyond the state-of-the-art: *COLLABS* ambition is to exploit the solid state-of-the-art related to AI-enabled solutions in cybersecurity in order to address the emerging challenges of IIoT-based collaborative manufacturing environments. ML- and DL-based solutions applied both in the cloud and at the edge will be deployed in order to ensure continuous assurance at runtime and throughout the manufacturing life cycle. It will combine RC and DL approaches to effectively navigate the essential trade-off between accuracy and performance making use of a wide range of available resources (IoT/edge/Cloud), and therefore apply a sophisticated AI approach tailor-made for IIoT challenges towards the *COLLABS* comprehensive cyber-intelligence framework for collaborative manufacturing.

8.2 Overview of research advances since March 2019

During the last year, a number of publications have demonstrated significant activity in the field of AI-enabled cybersecurity solutions in Industrial IoT environments. In that framework, Carames and Lamas' research "Blockchain to the next generation of cybersecure industry," illustrates that one of the core technologies that improves modern industrialization and is expected to have significant impact in the upcoming years in that field is blockchain, which provides value by adding trust, security, and decentralization to different industrial fields. Along with these benefits, blockchain-based Industry 4.0 proves valuable in terms of resource management and to be highly flexible to adapt in the rapidly changing production requirement (Fernández-Caramés and Fraga-Lamas, 2019).

The work by Gupta et al. (2019) describes a new mathematical model and heuristic algorithm to minimize the total cost in a multiple machine environment which enables the industries to take economically better decisions and effectively use their resources. A heuristic algorithm is developed for identical machines which process with the same tool. A system in which jobs with stochastic workloads arrive randomly and upon arrival, their workload is facilitated by IoT. The proposed algorithm determines the assignment of workload to the machine and processing speed. The algorithm works for both online and offline frameworks. Another paper published by Rholam et al. (2019) under the title "Smart Device for Multi-band Industrial IoT Communications" aims to expand the horizons of smart factories by proposing a communication model based on "Modbus" and multiband communication using NB-IoT: this communication

model allows data to be exchanged between different industrial equipment (PLCs, SCADA systems, etc.) via MODBUS RTU and ASCII, via RS485, or via analog and digital inputs for sensors and actuators.

However, using AI and IoT can affect business performance if not protected properly. In the research Cybersecurity in the context of industry 4.0, Corallo et al. (2020) propose a structured classification of critical industrial assets within Industry 4.0 and potential adverse impacts on business performance due to breaches of cybersecurity. In particular, cybersecurity in this work is analysed in terms of loss of confidentiality, integrity and availability of data associated with networked manufacturing machines. It is also suggested how critical assets and business impacts are correlated and how business impacts can be assessed. The proposed results can be organized in four steps for supporting companies in making decisions on cybersecurity policies. Finally, Mourtzis et al. (2019) in their research try to identify and map the potential vulnerable endpoints in a common industrial paradigm, where data will cross during aggregation and propose a robust way of securing a wireless sensor network by ensuring the integrity and authenticity of the parcels and the identity of the users. The vulnerabilities of a data acquisition system applied in the laser machine industry are mapped and presented in that paper.

A thorough research thread has been investigating the implementation of learning systems distributed over heterogeneous resources, such as machine learning over the fog and distributed deep learning systems embedded both on cloud and IoT devices (Lim et al., 2019; Lauri et al., 2019).

In cloud-centric architectural model, current AI methods and especially ML algorithms assume computations are conducted in a homogeneous cloud with ample computational and data storage resources available. In particular, AI's cloud-centric architectural model requires transmitting data from the end-user devices to the cloud, consuming significant data transmission resources and introducing latencies. EdgeAI is a joint consideration of edge computing and AI methods that improves both fields.

Lauri et al. (2019) aim to identify the challenges and detail the potential benefits of AI at the edge, building a coherent and overarching vision of what distributed artificial intelligence means in the context of edge computing. The authors consider edge-native AI to provide edge applications with access to secure, and distributed application-specific AI methods. It is assumed that EdgeAI solutions will enable radical innovation in collaborative IIoT, context-aware mobile technologies and so forth.

In the following, we shed a light to the distributed machine learning methods that have been addressed in the literature.

One of the current distributed ML methods is federated learning (FL). FL is a machine learning setting where the goal is to train a high-quality centralized model while training data remains distributed over a large number of clients each with unreliable and relatively slow network connections. In this context, federated learning paradigm provides an approach to handle aspects of collaborative and distributed learning, allowing sharing and generalization of personalized models acquired by multiple ML models' deployments and creating new pathways towards the application of AI-enabled solutions to address advanced cybersecurity challenges. Yao et al. (2019) consider learning algorithms for this setting where on each round, each client independently computes an update to the current model based on its local data, and communicates this update to a central server, where the client-side updates are aggregated to compute a new global model.

Wang S. et al. (2019) propose a federated learning system in resource constrained edge computing systems. It is challenging to perform distributed machine learning on resource

constrained MEC systems. In particular, the authors address the problem of how to efficiently utilize the limited computation and communication resources at the edge for the optimal learning performance. The authors consider an edge computing architecture where edge nodes are interconnected with the remote cloud via gateways and routers. The raw data is collected and stored at multiple edge nodes, and a machine learning model is trained from the distributed data without sending the raw data from the nodes to a central place. The authors focus on gradient-descent based federated learning algorithms, which have general applicability to a wide range of machine learning models. The learning process includes local update steps where each edge node performs gradient descent to adjust the (local) model parameter to minimize the loss function defined on its own dataset. The authors propose an algorithm to determine the frequency of global aggregation so that the available resource is most efficiently used.

In the same context, Yao et al. (2019) focus on the optimization algorithm in such settings, since the federating averaging suffers from heaving communication cost and inevitable performance drop. The method is based on a feature fusion to address this problem. In particular, they aggregate the features from both the local and global models, to achieve a higher accuracy at less communication cost. Furthermore, the feature fusion modules offer better initialization for newly incoming clients and thus speed up the process of convergence.

Tao et al. (2020) demonstrate that privacy and robustness protections destroy the accuracy of federated models for many individual participants removing their main incentive to join federated learning. Lauri et al. (2019) present detailed surveys on federated learning in mobile edge networks. In particular, they highlight the aforementioned challenges of FL implementation and review existing solutions. They present the applications of FL for mobile edge network optimization, and discuss the important challenges and future research directions in FL.

For more details about the federated learning methods, challenges and future directions, we refer the reader to research papers by Li et al. (2019) and Lim et al. (2019) that have provided an overview of federated learning, where statistical models are trained at the edge in distributed networks. They compare it with traditional distributed data centre computing and classical privacy-preserving learning.

8.3 Overview of innovative commercial products released since March 2019

Considering that there are billions of mobile devices in IIoT, distributed ML has the potential to disrupt cloud computing, the dominant computing paradigm today.

Google has released their first production-level federated learning platform, which has spawn many federated learning-based applications such as on-device item ranking, next-word prediction, and content suggestion. A Google paper has proposed a scalable production system for federated learning to enable increasing workload and output through the addition of resources such as compute, storage, bandwidth, etc.

Another commercial product is H2O that is a fully open source, distributed in-memory machine learning platform with linear scalability (<https://www.h2o.ai/products/h2o/>). H2O uses statistical and machine learning algorithms including gradient boosted machines, generalized linear models, and deep learning. This platform also has an industry leading AutoML functionality that automatically runs through all the algorithms and their hyperparameters.

9 Conclusion

In the preceding sections, this deliverable has clearly shown that many relevant works have been published and a fair number of practical systems introduced since the date of project proposal submission. However, none of these publications and systems offer “solved problems” that would invalidate projected *COLLABS* SotA advancements. Moreover, the published works and systems provide an improved foundation for *COLLABS* implementation compared to the state of affairs in March 2019.

What is evident from the provided SotA overview is that a comprehensive cyber-intelligence framework at the scale of *COLLABS* has yet to emerge not only in the domain of manufacturing systems, but in other more or less related areas as well. Successful implementation of *COLLABS* as a whole may, therefore, produce a rippling effect which instigates the development of comparable frameworks in various other domains, thereby providing additional long-term value to the *COLLABS* project.

References

- Abera, et al. (2016). C-flat: Control-flow attestation for embedded systems. ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security.
- Adams, D. et al., (Jan 2020). System and method for distributed ledger-based software supply chain management. U.S., Patent No. U.S. Patent Application No. 16/513,114.
- Al Shorman, A., Faris, H. and Aljarah, I. (2019) Unsupervised intelligent system based on one class support vector machine and Grey Wolf optimization for IoT botnet detection. J Ambient Intell Human Comput.
- Almaguer-Angeles, F., J. Murphy, L. Murphy and A. O. Portillo-Dominguez (2019). Choosing Machine Learning Algorithms for Anomaly Detection in Smart Building IoT Scenarios. IEEE 5th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT), Limerick, Ireland, pp. 491-495.
- Alshehri, M. and Panda, B. (Jan 2020). A Blockchain-Encryption-Based Approach to Protect Fog Federations from Rogue Nodes. arXiv preprint arXiv:2001.04490.
- Anderson, B., and McGrew, D. (2016). Identifying encrypted malware traffic with contextual flow data. ACM Workshop on Artificial Intelligence and Security, pp. 35-46.
- Apthorpe, N. et al. (2017). Spying on the Smart Home: Privacy Attacks and Defenses on Encrypted IoT Traffic, s.l.: [Online]. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1708.05044>.
- Apthorpe, N., D. Y., Yuxing, H., Reismanreism, D. and Feamster, N. (2019). Keeping the Smart Home Private with Smart(er) IoT Traffic Shaping. s.l., Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PET).
- BBC News (Dec 2014). Hack attack causes 'massive damage' at steel works. <https://www.bbc.com/news/technology-30575104>.
- Badrinarayanan, S., Jain, A., Ostrovsky, R. and Visconti, I. (Nov 2019). Paper: UC-Secure Multiparty Computation from One-Way Functions Using Stateless Tokens, s.l.: s.n.
- Bazuhair, W. and W. Lee (2020). Detecting Malign Encrypted Network Traffic Using Perlin Noise and Convolutional Neural Network. 10th Annual Computing and Communication Workshop and Conference (CCWC), Las Vegas, NV, USA, pp. 0200-0206.
- Bellare, M., K. G. Paterson, and P. Rogaway (2014). Security of symmetric encryption against mass surveillance. Annual Cryptology Conference (CRYPTO).
- Belmonte-Hernández, A., G. Hernández-Peñaloza, D. Martín Gutiérrez and F. Álvarez (2019). SWiBluX: Multi-Sensor Deep Learning Fingerprint for Precise Real-Time Indoor Tracking. IEEE Sensors Journal, vol. 19, no. 9, pp. 3473-3486.
- Benhamouda, F., Halevi, S. and Halevi, T. (Apr 2019). Supporting private data on Hyperledger Fabric with secure multiparty computation. 63(2/3).
- Bentov, I. et al. (2019). Real-Time Cryptocurrency Exchange Using Trusted Hardware. ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security (CCS'19).
- Bhatia, R., S. Benno, J. Esteban, T. V. Lakshman, and J. Grogan (2019). Unsupervised machine learning for network-centric anomaly detection in IoT. In Proceedings of the 3rd ACM CoNEXT Workshop on Big DATA, Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence for Data Communication Networks (Big-DAMA '19). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 42–48.

- Bienhaus, D., L. Jäger, R. Rieke and C. Krauß (2019). Gateway for Industrial Cyber-Physical Systems with Hardware-Based Trust Anchors. International Symposium on Intelligent and Distributed Computing, Springer, 2019, pp. 521-528.
- Boyle, E., Kohl, L. and Scholl, P. (Apr 2019). Homomorphic Secret Sharing from Lattices Without FHE, s.l.: s.n.
- Cerdeira, D., Santos, N., Fonseca, P., and Pinto, S. (May 2020). SoK: Understanding the Prevailing Security Vulnerabilities in TrustZone-assisted TEE Systems. IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (S&P), San Francisco, CA, USA, pp. 18-20.
- Chamarajnar, R. and A. Ashok (2019). Integrity Threat Identification for Distributed IoT in Precision Agriculture. 16th Annual IEEE International Conference on Sensing, Communication, and Networking (SECON), Boston, MA, USA, 2019, pp. 1-9.
- Chandran, N., Gupta, D., Rastogi, A. and Sharma, R. (Feb 2019). EzPC: Programmable, Efficient, and Scalable Secure Two-Party Computation for Machine Learning, s.l.: s.n.
- Chen, L., X. Yang, P. X. Liu and C. Li (2019) A Novel Outlier Immune Multipath Fingerprinting Model for Indoor Single-Site Localization. IEEE Access, vol. 7, pp. 21971-21980.
- Cheruvu, S., Kumar, A., Smith, N., and Wheeler, D. M. (2020). Base Platform Security Hardware Building Blocks. In Demystifying Internet of Things Security (pp. 149-212). Apress Open, Berkeley, CA.
- CISCO (2020). Cisco Stealthwatch Enterprise Data Sheet. [Online] <https://www.cisco.com/c/en/us/products/collateral/security/stealthwatch/datasheet-c78-739398.html>
- Corallo, A., M. Lazoi, and M. Lezzi (2020). Cybersecurity in the Context of Industry 4.0: A Structured Classification of Critical Assets and Business Impacts. Computers in Industry 114:103165.
- Costache, A., Laine, K. and Player, R. (May 2019). Homomorphic noise growth in practice: comparing BGV and FV, s.l.: s.n.
- De Carli, L., Torres, R., Modelo-Howard, G., Tongaonkar, A., and Jha, S. (2017). Botnet protocol inference in the presence of encrypted traffic. INFOCOM 2017-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications, pp. 1-9.
- De Lucia, M. J. and C. Cotton (2019). Detection of Encrypted Malicious Network Traffic using Machine Learning. IEEE Military Communications Conference (MILCOM), Norfolk, VA, USA, pp. 1-6.
- DeNisco Rayome, A. (2017). DDoS attacks increased 91% in 2017 thanks to IoT. <https://www.techrepublic.com/article/ddos-attacks-increased-91-in-2017-thanks-to-iot/>
- Deyannis, D. et al. (2020). TrustAV: Practical and Privacy-Preserving Malware Analysis in the Cloud. Tenth ACM Conference on Data and Application Security and Privacy (CODASPY '20).
- Eisen, M., C. Zhang, L. F. O. Chamon, D. D. Lee and A. Ribeiro (2019). Learning Optimal Resource Allocations in Wireless Systems. IEEE Transactions on Signal Processing, vol. 67, no. 10, pp. 2775-2790.
- Eisen, M. and A. Ribeiro (2019). Large Scale Wireless Power Allocation with Graph Neural Networks. IEEE 20th International Workshop on Signal Processing Advances in Wireless Communications (SPAWC), Cannes, France, pp. 1-5.

- Ekramifard, A. et al. (Mar 2020). A systematic literature review of integration of blockchain and artificial intelligence. In *Blockchain Cybersecurity, Trust and Privacy*.
- Elhabob, R., Zhao, Y., Sella, I. and Xiong, H. (Jun 2019). An efficient certificateless public key cryptography with authorized equality test in IIoT. *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*.
- Enck, W., Gilbert, P., Han, S., Tendulkar, V., Chun, B.G., Cox, L.P., Jung, J., McDaniel, P., Sheth, A.N. (2014). Taintdroid: an information-flow tracking system for realtime privacy monitoring on smartphones. *ACM Transactions on Computer Systems (TOCS)* 32(2):5.
- Ezeme, O. M. Q. H. Mahmoud and A. Azim (2019). A Deep Learning Approach to Distributed Anomaly Detection for Edge Computing. 18th IEEE International Conference On Machine Learning And Applications (ICMLA), Boca Raton, FL, USA, pp. 992-999.
- Falcone, R. (Nov 2016) Shamoon 2: Return of the Disttrack Wiper. <https://researchcenter.paloaltonetworks.com/2016/11/unit42-shamoon-2-return-disttrack-wiper/>.
- Fernández-Caramés, T. M. and Fraga-Lamas, P. (May 2018) A Review on the Use of Blockchain for the Internet of Things. *IEEE Access* 6:32979–33001.
- Fernández-Caramés, T. M., and Fraga-Lamas, P. (2019). A Review on the Application of Blockchain to the Next Generation of Cybersecure Industry 4.0 Smart Factories.” *IEEE Access* 7:45201–18.
- Frey, M., C. Gündoğan, P. Kietzmann, M. Lenders, H. Petersen, T. C. Schmidt, F. Juraschek and M. Wahlisch. (2019) Security for the Industrial IoT: The case for information-centric networking. *IEEE 5th World Forum on Internet of Things (WF-IoT)*, IEEE, pp. 424-429
- Fruhlinger, J. (Aug. 2018) What is WannaCry ransomware, how does it infect, and who was responsible? <https://www.csoonline.com/article/3227906/what-is-wannacry-ransomware-how-does-it-infect-and-who-was-responsible.html>.
- Furfaro, A. et al. (Apr 2019). An infrastructure for service accountability based on digital identity and blockchain 3.0. In *IEEE INFOCOM 2019-IEEE Conference on Computer Communications Workshops (INFOCOM WKSHPS)*.
- Garg, S., K. Kaur, S. Batra, G. Kaddoum, N. Kumar, A. Boukerche (2020). A multi-stage anomaly detection scheme for augmenting the security in IoT-enabled applications. *Future Generation Computer Systems*, 104:105-118.
- Garlati, C. and Pinto, S. (2020). A Clean Slate Approach to Linux Security RISC-V Enclaves. *Embedded World Exhibition & Conference*.
- Gonczol, P., Katsikouli, P., Herskind, L. and Dragoni, N. (Jan 2020). Blockchain Implementations and Use Cases for Supply Chains-A Survey. *IEEE Access*.
- Gupta, E. V., D. G. Mogale, and M. K. Tiwar (2019). Optimal Control of Production and Maintenance Operations in Smart Custom Manufacturing Systems with Multiple Machines. 9th IFAC Conference on Manufacturing Modelling, Management and Control – MIM ‘19, Berlin.
- Hardjono, T. and Smith, N. (2019). Decentralized Trusted Computing Base for Blockchain Infrastructure Security. *Frontiers in Blockchain Journal*.
- Hassan, M. M., A. Gumaei, S. Huda and A. Almogren (2020). Increasing the trustworthiness in the Industrial IoT Networks through a reliable cyber-attack detection model. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*.

- Hirschmann (2015). Communication Technologies for the Smart Factory of the Future – white paper. [Online] <https://industryofthingsvoice.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/05/White-Paper-Communication-Technologies-for-the-Smart-Factory-IIOT-I4.0.pdf>
- Huang, J., L. Kong, G. Chen, M.-Y. Wu, X. Liu and P. Zeng (2019). Towards secure industrial IoT: Blockchain system with credit-based consensus mechanism. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 15, pp. 3680-3689.
- Ibrahim A., Sadeghi AR., Tsudik G. (2019). HEALD: HEaling & Attestation for Low-End Embedded Devices. In: Goldberg I., Moore T. (eds) *Financial Cryptography and Data Security. FC 2019. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 11598. Springer
- ICS-CERT (Feb 2016). Cyber-Attack Against Ukrainian Critical Infrastructure. <https://ics-cert.us-cert.gov/alerts/IR-ALERT-H-16-056-01>.
- Jin, X. et al. (2019). Cloud virtual machine lifecycle security framework based on trusted computing. *Tsinghua Science and Technology*, vol. 24, no. 5, pp. 520-534.
- Karunaratne, S. and H. Gacanin (2019). An Overview of Machine Learning Approaches in Wireless Mesh Networks. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 57, no. 4, pp. 102-108.
- Kennedy, S. et al. (2019). I Can Hear Your Alexa: Voice Command Fingerprinting on Smart Home Speakers. s.l., *IEEE Conference on Communications and Network Security*.
- Kharchenko, V., S. Dotsenko, O. Illiashenko and S. Kamenskyi (2019). Integrated Cyber Safety & Security Management System: Industry 4.0 Issue. 10th International Conference on Dependable Systems, Services and Technologies (DESSERT), IEEE, pp. 197-201.
- Krawiecka, K., A. Kurnikov, A. Paverd, M. Mannan, and N. Asokan (2017). Protecting Web passwords from rogue servers using trusted execution environments. *International Conference on the World Wide Web, WWW*, pp. 1–16.
- Kuang, B., A. Fu, S. Yu, G. Yang, M. Su and Y. Zhang (2019). ESDRA: An Efficient and Secure Distributed Remote Attestation Scheme for IoT Swarms. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, no. 5, pp. 8372-8383.
- Lauri et al. (2019). EdgeAI: A Vision for Distributed, Edge-native Artificial Intelligence in Future 6G Networks. *6G Wireless Summit*.
- Lee, H., S. H. Lee, T. Q. S. Quek and I. Lee (2019). Deep Learning Framework for Wireless Systems: Applications to Optical Wireless Communications. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 57, no. 3, pp. 35-41.
- Lee, J., M. Azamfar and J. Singh (2019). A blockchain enabled Cyber-Physical System architecture for Industry 4.0 manufacturing systems. *Manufacturing Letters*, vol. 20, pp. 34-39.
- Leong, C., Treat, D. B. and Eyerhan, A. T. (Nov 2019). Distributed ledger based identity and origins of supply chain application enabling financial inclusion and sustainability. U.S., Patent No. U.S. Patent Application No. 16/115,705.
- Letaief, K. B., W. Chen, Y. Shi, J. Zhang and Y. A. Zhang (2019). The Roadmap to 6G: AI Empowered Wireless Networks. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 57, no. 8, pp. 84-90.
- Leuze electronic (2019). Fit for industry 4.0 with smart sensor business 4.0 – white paper. [Online] http://leuze.fr/media/assets/whitepaper/WP_I40_Smart_Sensor_Business_40_en.pdf
- Li, T., Anit, K. S., Ameet, T. and Smith, V. (2019). Federated Learning: Challenges, Methods, and Future Directions, arXiv:1908.07873.

- Lim, W. Y. et al. (2019). Federated Learning in Mobile Edge Networks: A Comprehensive Survey. arXiv:1909.11875.
- Liu, J., Z. Tian, R. Zheng and L. Liu (2019). A Distance-Based Method for Building an Encrypted Malware Traffic Identification Framework. *IEEE Access*, vol. 7, pp. 100014-100028.
- Liu, Y., A. Liu, X. Liu and M. Ma (2019). A trust-based active detection for cyber-physical security in industrial environments. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*, vol. 15, no. IEEE, pp. 6593-6603.
- Loupos, K., B. Caglayan, A. Papageorgiou, B. Starynkevitch, F. Vedrine, C. Skoufis, S. Christofi, B. Karakostas, A. Mygiakis, G. Theofilis, A. Chiappetta, H. Avgoustidis and G. Boulougouris (2019). Cognition Enabled IoT Platform for Industrial IoT Safety, Security and Privacy—The CHARIOT Project,” *IEEE 24th International Workshop on Computer Aided Modeling and Design of Communication Links and Networks (CAMAD)*, pp. 1-4.
- Mehmet, D., Turetken, O. and Ferwom, A. (Dec 2019). Blockchain and IoT for Delivery Assurance on Supply Chain (BIDAS). *IEEE International Conference on Big Data (Big Data)*.
- Mitra, G. et al. (2019). White Mirror: Leaking Sensitive Information from Interactive Netflix Movies using Encrypted Traffic Analysis. s.l., *ACM SIGCOMM*.
- Moghim, D., Sunar, B., Eisenbarth, T. and Heninger, N. (2020) TPM-FAIL: TPM meets Timing and Lattice Attacks. *29th USENIX Security Symposium (Usenix SEC 2020)*.
- Mourtzis, D., K. Angelopoulos, and V. Zogopoulos (2019). Mapping Vulnerabilities in the Industrial Internet of Things Landscape. *Procedia CIRP* 84:265–70.
- Msadek, N., Soua, R. and Engel, T. (2019). IoT Device Fingerprinting: Machine Learning based Encrypted Traffic Analysis. s.l., *IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference (WCNC)*.
- Müller, N.; Debus, P.; Kowatsch, D. and Böttinger, K. (2019). Distributed Anomaly Detection of Single Mote Attacks in RPL Networks. In *Proceedings of the 16th International Joint Conference on e-Business and Telecommunications - Volume 2: SECURE*, pages 378-385.
- Munir, M., M. A. Chattha, A. Dengel and S. Ahmed (2019). A Comparative Analysis of Traditional and Deep Learning-Based Anomaly Detection Methods for Streaming Data. *18th IEEE International Conference On Machine Learning And Applications (ICMLA)*, Boca Raton, FL, USA, 2019, pp. 561-566.
- Nguyen, T. D., S. Marchal, M. Miettinen, H. Fereidooni, N. Asokan and A. Sadeghi (2019). D²IoT: A Federated Self-learning Anomaly Detection System for IoT. *IEEE 39th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS)*, Dallas, TX, USA, 2019, pp. 756-767.
- Park, J., S. Samarakoon, M. Bennis and M. Debbah (2019). Wireless Network Intelligence at the Edge. *Proceedings of the IEEE*, vol. 107, no. 11, pp. 2204-2239.
- Qiu, P. et al. (2019). VoltJockey: Breaching TrustZone by Software-Controlled Voltage Manipulation over Multi-core Frequencies. *ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security (CCS '19)*.
- Quek, Y. T., Woo, Wai Lok and Logenthiran, T. (2020) IoT Load Classification and Anomaly Warning in ELV DC Pico-grids using Hierarchical Extended k-Nearest Neighbors. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, 7 (2). pp. 863-873.

- Rabbani, M. M., J. Vliegen, J. Winderickx, M. Conti and N. Mentens (2019). SHeLA: Scalable Heterogeneous Layered Attestation. *IEEE Internet of Things Journal*, vol. 6, no. 6, pp. 10240-10250.
- Rahman, M. S. et al. (2019). Tik-Tok: The Utility of Packet Timing in Website Fingerprinting Attacks. s.l., [Online]. <http://arxiv.org/abs/1902.06421>.
- Reed, A. and Kranch, M. (2017). Identifying HTTPS-Protected Netflix Videos in Real-Time. s.l., in *Proceedings of the Seventh ACM on Conference on Data and Application Security and Privacy – CODASPY*.
- Rezaeibagha, F. et al. (Sept 2019). Fully secure lightweight certificateless signature scheme for IIoT. *IEEE Access*.
- Rholam, O., M. Tabaa, and F. Monteiro Et Abbas Dandache (2019). Smart Device for Multi-Band Industrial IoT Communications. *Procedia Computer Science* 155:660–65.
- Rouhani, S. and Deters, R. (Oct 2019). Blockchain based access control systems: State of the art and challenges. In *IEEE/WIC/ACM International Conference on Web Intelligence*.
- Roy, S. S. et al. (Feb 2019). FPGA-based High-Performance Parallel Architecture for Homomorphic Computing on Encrypted Data, s.l.: s.n.
- Samani, E., P. Khaledian, A. Aligholian, E. Papalexakis, S. Cun, M. H. Nazari, and H. Mohsenian-Rad (2020). Anomaly Detection in IoT-Based PIR Occupancy Sensors to Improve Building Energy Efficiency. University of California, <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/8h90c81b>
- Sani, A. S. et al. (Oct 2019). Xyreum: A High-Performance and Scalable Blockchain for IIoT Security and Privacy. In *2019 IEEE 39th International Conference on Distributed Computing Systems (ICDCS)*.
- Schuster, R., Shmatikov, V. and Tromer, E. (2017). Beauty and the Burst: Remote Identification of Encrypted Video Streams. s.l., *USENIX Conference on Security Symposium*.
- Schwarz, M. et al. (2019). Practical Enclave Malware with Intel SGX. *Detection of Intrusions and Malware, and Vulnerability Assessment: 16th International Conference (DIMVA'19)*.
- Sciancalepore, S., Ibrahim, O., Oligeri, G. and Pietro, R. D. (2019). Detecting Drones Status via Encrypted Traffic Analysis. s.l., *ACM Workshop on Wireless Security and Machine Learning*.
- Sechkova, T. et al. (2019). Cloud & edge trusted virtualized infrastructure manager (vim)-security and trust in openstack. *IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference Workshop (WCNCW)*.
- Shi, Y. et al. (Jul 2019). SDSRS: A Novel White-Box Cryptography Scheme for Securing Embedded Devices in IIoT. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics*.
- Shi, Y., K. Davaslioglu, Y. E. Sagduyu, W. C. Headley, M. Fowler and G. Green (2019). Deep Learning for RF Signal Classification in Unknown and Dynamic Spectrum Environments. *IEEE International Symposium on Dynamic Spectrum Access Networks (DySPAN)*, Newark, NJ, USA, pp. 1-10.
- Shukla, R. M. and S. Sengupta (2020). Scalable and Robust Outlier Detector using Hierarchical Clustering and Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Neural Network for the Internet of Things. *Internet of Things*, Volume 9, 100167.

- Sirinam, P., Imani, M., Juarez, M. and Wright, M. (2018). Deep Fingerprinting: Undermining Website Fingerprinting Defenses with Deep Learning. s.l., ACM SIGSAC Conference on Computer and Communications Security (CCS).
- Skarlatos, D. et al. (2019). MicroScope: enabling microarchitectural replay attacks. 46th International Symposium on Computer Architecture (ISCA '19).
- Soltani, R., Goeckel, D., Towsley, D. and Houmansadr, A. (2020). Fundamental Limits of Invisible Flow Fingerprinting. *IEEE Transactions on Information Forensics and Security*, Volume 15, pp. 345-360.
- Song, D. L. et al. (2020). Keystone: An Open Framework for Architecting Trusted Execution Environments. Fifteenth European Conference on Computer Systems (EuroSys '20).
- Sun, Y., M. Peng, Y. Zhou, Y. Huang and S. Mao (2019). Application of Machine Learning in Wireless Networks: Key Techniques and Open Issues. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 4, pp. 3072-3108.
- Tao, Y., Bagdasarayan, E. and Shmatikov, V. (2020). Salvaging federated learning by local adaptation. arXiv:2002.04758.
- Van Bulck, J. et al. (2018). Foreshadow: Extracting the Keys to the Intel SGX Kingdom with Transient Out-of-order Execution. USENIX.
- Wang, J., C. Jiang, H. Zhang, Y. Ren, K. Chen and L. Hanzo (2020). Thirty Years of Machine Learning: The Road to Pareto-Optimal Wireless Networks. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials* (early access).
- Wang, L., Li, J., Bhatti, U. A., Liu, Y. (2019) Anomaly Detection in Wireless Sensor Networks Based on KNN. In: Sun X., Pan Z., Bertino E. (eds) *Artificial Intelligence and Security. ICAIS 2019. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 11634. Springer
- Wang, S. et al. (2019). Adaptive Federated Learning in Resource Constrained Edge Computing Systems. *IEEE Journal on Selected Areas in Communications*, vol. 37, no. 6, pp. 1205-1221.
- Wang, W. et al. (May 2019). Toward Scalable Fully Homomorphic Encryption Through Light Trusted Computing Assistance, s.l.: s.n.
- Wang, W. and Stöttinger, M. (2020) Post-Quantum Secure Architectures for Automotive Hardware Secure Modules. *Cryptology ePrint archive* 2020/026.
- Wang, X., Chen, S. and Jajodia, a. S. (2005). Tracking anonymous peer-to-peer VoIP calls on the internet. s.l., 12th ACM conference on Computer and communications security - CCS.
- Wu, D., Z. Jiang, X. Xie, X. Wei, W. Yu and R. Li. (2019) LSTM Learning with Bayesian and Gaussian Processing for Anomaly Detection in Industrial IoT. *IEEE Transactions on Industrial Informatics* (early access).
- Wu G. et al. (2019) A Fast kNN-Based Approach for Time Sensitive Anomaly Detection over Data Streams. In: Rodrigues J. et al. (eds) *Computational Science – ICCS 2019. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol 11537. Springer
- Xiao, X., Wu, T., Chen, Y. and Fan, X. (Oct 2019). Privacy-Preserved Approximate Classification Based on Homomorphic Encryption, s.l.: s.n.
- Xu, W. et al. (May 2019). Attack and Improvement on a Symmetric Fully Homomorphic Encryption Scheme, s.l.: s.n.

- Xu, Y. et al. (Feb 2020). Blockchain-Enabled Accountability Mechanism Against Information Leakage in Vertical Industry Services. *IEEE Transactions on Network Science and Engineering*.
- Yan, W., A. Fu, Y. Mu, X. Zhe, S. Yu, and B. Kuang (2019). EAPA: Efficient Attestation Resilient to Physical Attacks for IoT Devices. In *Proceedings of the 2nd International ACM Workshop on Security and Privacy for the Internet-of-Things (IoT S&P'19)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2–7.
- Yao, X., T. Huang, C. Wu, R. Zhang and L. Sun (2019). Towards Faster and Better Federated Learning: A Feature Fusion Approach. *IEEE International Conference on Image Processing (ICIP)*, Taipei, Taiwan, pp. 175-179.
- Yu, X. and Guo, H. (Aug. 2019). A Survey on IIoT Security. In *2019 IEEE VTS Asia Pacific Wireless Communications Symposium (APWCS)*.
- Yu, T., Y. Sun, S. Nanda, V. Sekar, and S. Seshan (2019). RADAR: A Robust Behavioral Anomaly Detection for IoT Devices in Enterprise Networks. *Carnegie Mellon University Technical Report CMU-CyLab-19-003*.
- Yu, Y. et al. (Oct 2019). Toward Data Security in Edge Intelligent IIoT. *IEEE Network*.
- Zappone, A., M. Di Renzo, M. Debbah, T. T. Lam and X. Qian (2019). Model-Aided Wireless Artificial Intelligence: Embedding Expert Knowledge in Deep Neural Networks for Wireless System Optimization. *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 14, no. 3, pp. 60-69.
- Zhang, A. and Bai, X. (Dec 2019). Decentralized Authorization and Authentication Based on Consortium Blockchain. In *International Conference on Blockchain and Trustworthy Systems*.
- Zhang, C., P. Patras and H. Haddadi (2019). Deep Learning in Mobile and Wireless Networking: A Survey. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 2224-2287.
- Zhang, L., Tan, T., Gong, Y., and Yang, W. (2019). Fingerprint Database Reconstruction Based on Robust PCA for Indoor Localization. *Sensors* 19(11):2537.
- Zhu, G., D. Liu, Y. Du, C. You, J. Zhang and K. Huang (2020). Toward an Intelligent Edge: Wireless Communication Meets Machine Learning. *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 58, no. 1, pp. 19-25.
- Zhu, R., X. Ji, D. Yu, Z. Tan, L. Zhao, J. Li and X. Xia (2020). KNN-Based Approximate Outlier Detection Algorithm Over IoT Streaming Data. *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 42749-42759.